

Contribution to the knowledge on the flora of Mt. Luboten, Sharri Mts., Kosovo

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Abstract: With the aim of improving the floristic knowledge of Kosovo, here we present an inventory of the plant taxa recorded and collected between the March 2015 and September 2019, in the mountain massif of Luboten, Sharri Mts., SE Kosovo. Field surveys were conducted repeatedly for four years, on each vegetation season. With this work we aimed to provide detailed data concerning the vascular flora richness and distributional patterns. Floristic samples were studied in all representative habitats and sites, concerning climate, exposition, altitude and bedrock composition. This research led to the identification of a total 853 plant taxa of vascular plants, belonging to 354 genera and 93 families. Among these taxa, 82 are Balkan endemics and 53 are included into the Red Book of Vascular Flora of Kosovo. Out of them, 4 are critically endangered, 16 endangered, 3 vulnerable, 8 near threatened and 22 least concern. On the basis of the available floristic literature, 2 plant taxa are found to be new for Kosovo: *Bromopsis cappadocica* subsp. *cappadocica* and *Pilosella macrotricha*. At a national scale, we have found new distribution records for 17 taxa and additionally for 2 plant taxa: *Ranunculus fontanus* and *Sesleria wettsteinii*, conservation suggestions are provided. All natural habitats were classified according to EUNIS and their floristic richness is herein provided. Furthermore, the corresponding EUNIS habitat(s) for each taxon of where it was recorded to be growing are also indicated.

Keywords: endemics, Kosovo, new floristic records, plant diversity, Sharri Mts.

Introduction

In terms of scientific knowledge and conservation measures, floristic studies are of substantial importance (Calabrese et al. 2018; Gentry 1978). Conservation strategies rely heavily on significant information provided by floristic studies, particularly concerning endemic plants, their threats and distribution patterns as well, upon which priorities and action measures are set (Orsenigo et al. 2018; Martin 2009). Studies with wild vascular plants especially during the last two decades in Kosovo were intensified and they were used to evaluate the long-term changes in floristic composition (Millaku et al. 2008; Millaku et al. 2017; Prodanović et al. 2018; Rexhepi et al. 2005; Rexhepi et al. 2009; Veselaj et al. 2006; etc.), in vegetation studies on mountain ecosystems (Amidžić et al. 2012; Berisha et al. 2019; Millaku et al. 2011; Millaku et al. 2012; Rexhepi 1994, etc.) as well as studies concerning the risk assessment ending up with the compilation of the Red list (Anonymous 2014a) and the Red Book of Vascular flora of the Republic of Kosovo (Millaku et al. 2013), among other aspects.

In the context of plant taxa richness and natural habitat diversity in Kosovo, Sharri Mts. represent a valuable and rather substantial biodiversity centre not only for Kosovo but for the whole Balkan Peninsula (Millaku et al. 2013; Micevski & Matevski 1987; Stevanović et al. 2007; Tomović et al. 2014). This mountain chain is estimated to be home of more than 1700 vascular plant taxa (Anonymous 2014b) and 115 and 128 Balkan endemics in two corresponding UTM squares - DM87 and DM97 respectively (Tomović et al. 2014). The first massif from the north-eastern side of the Sharri Mountains is the Mountain of Luboten, which has proven to be very interesting and rich in terms of its floristic and phyto-geographic composition, based on different studies (Horvat et al. 1974; Rajevski 1990; Rexhepi 1984; Vogt et al. 2018). Mt. Luboten (in Albanian Luboten/Lybeten, in Macedonian Ljuboten) is located in the SE Kosovo at the border area between Kosovo and Northern Macedonia (Fig. 1). It represents the highest mountain massif on the NE side of the Sharri Mts. (2.498 m a.s.l) and as a mountain area it is characterized by unique high-mountain ecosystem with a diverse regional montane to alpine flora, with plenty of endemorelic and glacial plant taxa. It differs from the surrounding mountain ranges in its bedrock composition, being mainly limestone with small and scattered silicate plates, that in other parts of the Sharri Mts. are more dominant (Anonymous 2013). With its surroundings, Luboten is also characterized by a modified continental climate with significant Mediterranean influence, reaching via the air currents through the Vardar and Lepenc valleys. Due to its high altitudes, Luboten is predominantly characterized by a typical mountain with alpine climates (Rexhepi 1984), whilst its weather also differing from other mountain massifs in the chain of Sharri Mountains.

The first floristic notes for Luboten date back on the first half of the 19th century, when Grisebach (1843) visited the mountain, followed by Dörfler (1894-1914) and Rohlena (1937). Moreover, a large number of plant taxa that are widespread in Sharri

Mts. are listed in the Floras of Serbia (Josifović 1970-1977; Sarić & Diklić 1986; Diklić & Stevanović 2012) and Northern Macedonia (Micevski 1985-2005; Matevski 2010), some of which are now being reported for Luboten. Horvat (1960) as well as Rajevski (1990) reported of some plant communities in Luboten, while Rexhepi (1984) contributed with additional floristic notes and mentions it too in the context of the general vegetation of Kosovo (Rexhepi 1994).

The research aims were to *i.* improve and update in detail the floristic knowledge of the Mt. Luboten, *ii.* review the presence of endemic taxa and their distribution across different habitats and *iii.* analyze the habitat types according to EUNIS and evaluate their general floristic richness.

In this work, the results of four year of the floristic field investigation in the Mt. Luboten and lab research are presented. According to Millaku et al. (2017) and Anonymous (2014b), the area of this mountain massif was among those in Kosovo for which the available floristic and vegetation data were particularly scarce.

Material and Methods

Study area

The study site, encompassing an area of ca 44 km², covers the Mt. Luboten entirely, a territory of the Sharri National Park, located at the border between Kosovo and N. Macedonia (Fig. 1). The mountain massif of Luboten is located between 42°11'–42°13'N and 21°07'–21°09'E in Kosovo. Administratively, it belongs to the municipalities of Kaçanik and Shtërpce in Kosovo and Jegunovce in Macedonia. The altitude ranges from 310 m a.s.l. at the shores of Lepenci River, to 2498 m a.s.l. at the top of the mountain. In vertical composition, from down up scale, mixed forests between broad-leaved deciduous forest (*Ostrya carpinifolia* Scop., *Carpinus orientalis* Mill. and *Fagus sylvatica* L.) and coniferous forest (*Abies alba* Mill. and *Picea abies* (L.) Karst), are followed by the beech forests up to 1550 m a.s.l., and from there up to the summit of the mountain, it is made predominantly out of grasslands, although there are also rocky cliffs and scree. Annual rainfall ranges between 900 and 1100 mm, and it is concentrated in the autumn-spring period with a maximum in November and a minimum in August (Çavolli 1997; Ivanović et al. 2016) and the average annual temperature of 7.6°C with the warmest month in summer (August) and the coldest in winter (January) (Çavolli 1997). The upper part of Mt Luboten is declared as a strict nature reserve, within the Sharri National Park (Anonymous 2015).

Methods

Field surveys were performed 32 to 36 times a year (subject to weather conditions), during four years consecutively, starting by the end of March until the end of September, with the aim of investigating the flora of Mt. Luboten. For accuracy reasons, mature plant taxa with full reproductive organs (e.g. flowers, fruits and spores) were carefully collected while immature plant material or those without

Fig. 1 Investigated area of the study.

reproductive organs at the moment of survey, were written down in a notebook, photographed and collected again in different vegetation period. Plant taxa identification and nomenclature were based mostly on Tutin & al. (1968-1980, 1993), Flora of Serbia (Josifović 1970-1977; Sarić & Diklić 1986; Stevanović 2012), Flora of Macedonia (Micevski 1985-2005; Matevski 2010) and Flora of Albania (Barina et al. 2018; Papparisto et al. 1988; Qosja et al. 1992, 1996; Vangjeli et al. 2000), while finally their nomenclature was updated according to Euro+Med Plantbase (Euro+Med 2006+). Collected plants were dried, mounted and prepared as voucher specimens following the standard guidelines (Bridson & Forman 1998). All plant specimens are deposited in the Herbarium of the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Prishtina, given a particular reference number (Annex I). The herbarium label of each taxon provides information about the global positioning system (GPS), habitat type, collection date, local name, and scientific nomenclature. In the working table (Annex I), we have added two columns, for two particular works on Luboten: Rexhepi (1984) and Rajevski (1990), for comparison reasons of floristic data. Certain plant taxa were not mention in any of these references, but those taxa were mentioned in the “Floras of Serbia”, so we did not indicate as new floristic data. In the Note column, we have listed our floristic records with the necessary data that are not mentioned anywhere on any of the currently available floristic literature sources. For identification of endemics, Tomović et al. (2014) and Petrova & Vladimirov (2010) were followed. To verify the conservation status of each taxon, the Red Book of Vascular flora of the Republic of Kosovo (Millaku et al. 2013) and the European Red List of Vascular Plants (Bilz et al. 2011) were checked. For taxa life

forms and chorological types, Pignatti (1982) was followed, with additional references concerning some local species to Gajić (1980) and Flora of Greece (Dimopoulos et al. 2016). Additionally, all surveyed natural habitats were classified according to EUNIS (EUNIS 2007) and each taxon is linked to its respective habitat type(s) where it was recorded. This was done mainly with the help of vegetation relevés that were done on the same time, encompassing all habitat types. The list of plant families follows that of Excursions flora of Germany (Jäger et al. 2013), while plant taxa within each family are listed alphabetically (Annex I).

Results

The checklist consists of 853 taxa (with 6 additional taxa treated separately as potentially reported in error - Tab. 1). They are distributed into 354 genera and 93 families. The most represented families are Asteraceae (98 taxa), Poaceae (69 taxa) and Caryophyllaceae (53 taxa). Among these taxa, 82 are Balkan endemics and 53 are included in the Red Book of Vascular Flora of Kosovo. Out of them, 4 were critically endangered (CR), 16 endangered (EN), 3 vulnerable (VU), 8 near threatened (NT) and 22 least concern (LC). Additionally, the European Red List of Vascular Plants, from this checklist includes 79 plant taxa, majority of them being LC (Tab. 2).

The biological spectrum of the surveyed flora shows a pronounced dominance of hemicryptophytes (58.5%) and then geophytes (12.3%), followed by therophytes (11.6%), chamaephytes (8.7%) and phanerophytes (8.7%).

Concerning chorological types, the checklist contains Euro-Asiatic 19.4%, Balkan 14.1%, Orof. European 12.9%, Euro-Mediterranean 9.3%, European 8.2%, Euro-Siberian 6.6%, Circumboreal 6.1%, with other chorological groups being represented with less than 5%.

On the basis of the available floristic literature, two plant taxa are found to be new for flora of Kosovo (Tab. 3). They are the following ones: 1. *Bromopsis cappadocica* (Boiss. & Balansa) Holub subsp. *cappadocica* and 2. *Pilosella macrotricha* (Boiss.) F. W. Schultz & Sch. Bip. Additionally, we report new distributional records for 17 plant taxa: 1. *Acer heldreichii* Orph. ex Boiss., 2. *Arabis ciliata* Clairv., 3. *Arabis hirsuta* (L.) Scop., 4. *Arabis serpyllifolia* Vill., 5. *Cardamine carnosa* Waldst. et Kit., 6. *Dianthus deltooides* subsp. *degenii* (Bald.) Strid., 7. *Dianthus gracilis* subsp. *armerioides* (Griseb.) Tutin, 8. *Erysimum comatum* Pančić, 9. *Festuca bosniaca* Kumm. & Sendtn., 10. *Festuca koritnicensis* Hayek & J. Vetter, 11. *Genista depressa* M. Bieb., 12. *Hieracium pilosum* subsp. *villosiceps* Gottschl., 13. *Juncus inflexus* L., 14. *Tanacetum larvatum* (Pant.) Hayek, 15. *Veronica austriaca* subsp. *teucrium* (L.) D. A. Webb, 16. *Veronica serpyllifolia* L. and 17. *Viola schariensis* Erben.

It is worth to note that according to relevant literature sources, some of these taxa were mentioned for Sharri Mts. and two of them also for Mt. Luboten, referring to the Macedonian part of the mountain massif, as the same taxa have not been reported for the flora of Kosovo. In our survey, we have recorded them also in the Kosovo side of the massif. These taxa are: *Dianthus deltooides* subsp. *degenii*; *Erysimum comatum* – mentioned for Sharri Mts. in Macedonia (Micevski 1995).

Cardamine carnosa was reported by Micevski (1995) on the macedonian side of the Mt. Luboten, *Genista depressa* was mentioned for Sharri Mts. in Macedonia (Micevski 2001), *Juncus inflexus* was mentioned for Sharri Mts. in Macedonia (Ade 1954), while *Veronica serpyllifolia* was mentioned for Luboten by Grisebach (1843).

Concerning the overall plant species richness and richness of the endemic plants, it turned out that Mt. Luboten is exceptionally rich in both terms. With 853 plant taxa (excluding 6 doubtful taxa), it alone accounts for more than 28% of the total of Kosovo vascular flora, since it is estimated that there are ca 3.000 of plant taxa in Kosovo (Millaku et al. 2013). Almost similar richness was observed in terms of endemic plants, given that 82 Balkan endemic taxa were recorded, as long as Kosovo is believed to have in total 367 Balkan endemic plant taxa (Tomović et al. 2014).

Regarding the EUNIS Habitat types, we have recorded 38 main habitat types, each of them divided into different sub-groups accordingly (Tab. 4). It was observed that on habitat type E1.2 (Perennial calcareous grassland and basic steppes) 29.8% of the recorded taxa were growing, followed by habitat type E4.4 (Calcareous alpine and subalpine grasslands) that held 25.9% of the recorded taxa, then E1.7 (Non-Mediterranean dry acid and neutral closed grassland) with 15.8%, G1.6 (*Fagus* woodland) with 13.4%, then E4.39 (Oro-Moesian acidophilous grasslands) with 12.5%, and G1.7 (Thermophilous deciduous woodland) with 11.7%. For other habitat types, associated plant taxa counted for less than 10% of the total number.

Ranunculus fontanus C. Presl was recorded in a very restricted habitat of waterlogged meadows on the mountain belt of Mt. Luboten. Population consisted of ca 40 mature individuals scattered in an area of 500 m². This species was particularly analyzed because it is listed on the Convention for Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (Council of Europe 1979). Furthermore, this locality represents the only species habitat in Kosovo.

Sesleria wettsteinii Dörf. & Hayek was recorded on a calcareous bedrock at an altitude of 2329 m a.s.l at a very restricted area of the alpine grasslands on the SE exposition of Luboten. It was growing in dense groups with no more than 25 mature individuals. Species area of occupancy was only 50 m². The nearest known locality of this Balkan endemic species is in Mt. Oshlak, Sharri Mts. (Krivošej 1997) some 20 km NW from Mt. Luboten.

Discussion

Plant diversity, distribution and conservation features

The substrates' physical and chemical features are reflected on the vascular flora composition. Predominant calcareous substrates on Mt. Luboten have greatly influenced the floristic diversity, particularly noted on grasslands, a phenomenon that has also been observed in similar studies on the region: Matevski & Kostadinovski (1999); Matevski et al. (2018) and Uzunov & Gussev (2003). Additionally, calcifuge and acidophilous taxa are also abundant, due to the presence of silicate soils.

Tab. 1 List of potentially doubtful plant taxa that were reported erroneously from Luboten, most probably referring to misidentified plant material.

No.	Taxa	Comment
1.	<i>Erysimum jugicola</i> Jord.	c. 01 – Species was reported by Rajevski (1990) but we assume that it must have been reported in error, because the natural distributional area of the species is France, Switzerland and Italy and it is not naturally distributed into the region of SE Europe. It most probably was referred to misidentified plant material from: <i>Erysimum comatum</i> Pančić.
2.	<i>Dianthus microlepis</i> Boiss.	c. 02 – Species was reported by Rexhepi (1984) but we assume that it must have been reported in error. <i>D. microlepis</i> is to be found only on the Albanian Alps of Kosovo and not on the Sharri Mts. (to whom Luboten belongs to). From this group in Sharri Mts. we have only <i>Dianthus scardicus</i> Wettst. and these two species are very similar in their general appearance. Our assumption is further supported by Diklić & Stevanović (2012).
3.	<i>Dianthus petraeus</i> Waldst. & Kit.	c. 03 – Species was reported by Rexhepi (1984) but we assume that it must have been reported in error, referring to misidentified plant material. <i>D. petraeus</i> is distributed into W and E Serbia, but it was never reported from Sharri Mts. It most probably was referred to misidentified plant material from: <i>Dianthus superbus</i> L.
4.	<i>Paronychia chionaea</i> Boiss.	c. 04 – Species was reported by Rajevski (1990) but we assume that it must have been reported in error, referring to misidentified plant material of <i>Paronychia macedonica</i> Chaudhri. Furthermore, <i>P. chionaea</i> is confined to N Greece, S Albania and S Macedonia (?), but is absent in our study region.
5.	<i>Pinguicula leptoceras</i> Rchb.	c. 05 – Species was reported by Rajevski (1990) but we assume that it must have been reported in error, referring to misidentified plant material of <i>Pinguicula balcanica</i> Casper. According to floristic studies of this genus in the Balkans (Shuka et al. 2007), these two species have been confused for a long time by botanists, mainly due to the fact that they have very slight morphological differences, for the most part on the width of their calyx lobes rounded at the apex.
6.	<i>Centaurea kosaninii</i> Hayek	c. 06 – This species was reported by Rexhepi (1984) but we assume that it might have been reported in error, due to the fact that <i>C. kosaninii</i> is an endemic serpentinophilic plant species. Furthermore in Luboten there are no serpentine soils, and the presence of the species on field was never confirmed during our field surveys. It is however present in the neighboring Mt. of Brezovica but not in Luboten.

Tab. 2 Number of recorded plant taxa, occurring in conservation lists. XK – Kosovo, EU – Europe.

IUCN Conservation status	XK	EU
Extinct (EX)		
Extinct in the Wild (EW)		
Critically Endangered (CR)	4	
Endangered (EN)	16	
Vulnerable (VU)	3	
Near Threatened (NT)	8	3
Conservation Dependent (CD)		
Least Concern (LC)	22	73
Data Deficient (DD)		3
Not Evaluated (NE)		

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Some of the recorded taxa have a very narrow distribution range: *Linaria alpina* (L.) Mill., *Sideritis scardica* Griseb. and *Aubrieta columnae* subsp. *croatica* (Schott & al.) Mattf., are plants that inhabit dry rocky places on calcareous substrate. All these species were encountered only for Luboten and nowhere else in Kosovo. They are also enlisted as critically endangered "CR" plant taxa in the Kosovo Red Book of Vascular Flora (Millaku et al. 2013). In addition, *Veronica thessalica* Benth. is another critically endangered plant taxon being recorded only in Luboten and Koritnik Mts. These abovementioned plants are also Balkan Endemics, which clearly demonstrates the importance of Mt. Luboten for Kosovo's floristic diversity.

Whenever a conservation planning is undertaken, an increased emphasis is put on floristic data, plant communities and their natural habitats. Special attention is given in this context to threatened, rare and endemic plants (Kendall & Snelson 2009). In this regard, bringing in data on the presence of two new plant taxa for the flora of Kosovo as well as new information on the distribution of seventeen other plant taxa constitutes a contribution of particular importance to the recognition of plant diversity in Kosovo.

Very interesting natural habitats, harboring plenty of endemic plants, are the vulnerable ones along the water streams at higher altitudes (E5.5 - Subalpine moist or wet tall-herb and fern stands). These habitats are proved to have very unique vegetation (Čarni & Matevski 2010) and therefore deserve proper treatment

Tab. 3 Data concerning the newly reported taxa for flora of Kosovo. Sampling site(s), geographical coordinates, collection dates along with other relevant data.

No.	Plant species	Coll. dates	Herbar.	Coordinates	Sampling site(s)	Additional notes
1.	<i>Bromopsis cappadocica</i> (Boiss. & Balansa) Holub subsp. <i>cappadocica</i>	10.06.2017 28.06.2018 03.07.2019	L-072	42°13.103 N; 021°08.544 E	Rocky grassland. On calcareous substrate. On S, SE and NE expositions alike.	Species was growing in a range of calcaeous grasslands, at altitudes from 1720 m. a.s.l., up to the summit of the mountain. Very well developed populations.
2.	<i>Pilosella macrotricha</i> (Boiss.) F. W. Schultz & Sch. Bip.	21.06.2016 14.06.2018	L-724	42°12.885 N; 021°08.124 E	Calcareous grasslands of the S, SE & SW slopes of the Mt. Recorded on different sites, from 1812 m up to 2080 m. a.s.l.	Scattered individuals across rocky gfrasslands.

Tab. 4 List of main recorded EUNIS Habitat types with their associated plant taxa in numbers and %.

No.	EUNIS	No. of taxa	%	Full EUNIS Habitat name
1.	D2.2	75	8.79	Poor fens and soft-water spring mires
2.	D2.3	44	5.16	Transition mires and quaking bogs
3.	D4.1	9	1.06	Rich fens, eutrophic tall-herb fens & calcareous flushes and soaks
4.	D4.2	9	1.06	Basic mountain flushes and streamsides, with a rich arctic-montane flora
5.	D5.131	4	0.47	<i>Typha latifolia</i> beds normally without free-standing water
6.	E1.112	18	2.11	<i>Sempervivum</i> or <i>Jovibarba</i> communities on rock debris
7.	E1.2	254	29.78	Perennial calcareous grassland and basic steppes
8.	E1.55	11	1.29	Eastern sub-Mediterranean dry grassland
9.	E1.7	135	15.83	Non-Mediterranean dry acid and neutral closed grassland
10.	E1.92	29	3.40	Perennial open siliceous grassland
11.	E3.3	23	2.70	Sub-mediterranean humid meadows
12.	E3.4	41	4.81	Moist or wet eutrophic and mesotrophic grassland

Tab. 4 - cont.

13.	E3.5	22	2.58	Moist or wet oligotrophic grassland
14.	E4.1	32	3.75	Vegetated snow-patch
15.	E4.31	36	4.22	Alpic <i>Nardus stricta</i> swards and related communities
16.	E4.34	50	5.86	Alpigenous acidophilous grassland
17.	E4.39	107	12.54	Oro-Moesian acidophilous grassland
18.	E4.4	221	25.91	Calcareous alpine and subalpine grassland
19.	E4.5	21	2.46	Alpine and subalpine enriched grassland
20.	E5.2	79	9.26	Thermophile woodland fringes
21.	E5.3	8	0.94	<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> fields
22.	E5.4	77	9.03	Moist or wet tall-herb and fern fringes and meadows
23.	E5.5	46	5.39	Subalpine moist or wet tall-herb and fern stands
24.	F2.1	13	1.52	Subarctic and alpine dwarf willow scrub
25.	F2.2	82	9.61	Evergreen alpine and subalpine heath and scrub
26.	F2.3	13	1.52	Subalpine deciduous scrub
27.	F3.2	69	8.09	Submediterranean deciduous thickets and brushes
28.	G1.1	8	0.94	Riparian and gallery woodland, with dominant <i>Alnus</i> , <i>Betula</i> , <i>Populus</i> or <i>Salix</i>
29.	G1.6	114	13.36	<i>Fagus</i> woodland
30.	G1.7	100	11.72	Thermophilous deciduous woodland
31.	G1.A1	78	9.14	<i>Quercus</i> - <i>Fraxinus</i> - <i>Carpinus betulus</i> woodland on eutrophic and mesotrophic soils
32.	G3.1	31	3.63	<i>Abies</i> and <i>Picea</i> woodland
33.	G4.6	39	4.57	Mixed <i>Abies</i> - <i>Picea</i> - <i>Fagus</i> woodland
34.	H2.3	12	1.41	Temperate-montane acid siliceous screes
35.	H2.4	41	4.81	Temperate-montane calcareous and ultra-basic screes
36.	H2.6	32	3.75	Calcareous and ultra-basic screes of warm exposures
37.	H3.1	23	2.70	Acid siliceous inland cliffs
38.	H3.2	25	2.93	Basic and ultra-basic inland cliffs

continuous monitoring. In some areas of the Mt. Luboten, it was noticed that water springs were altered by humans. If not managed properly, there is a great risk that these habitats will be irreversibly disrupted.

When it comes to plant conservation, it should be noted that there are two taxa that deserve additional treatment in future works, when the Kosovo Red List of Plants will be updated. *Ranunculus fontanus* C. Presl with a single and very narrow habitat of only 40 individuals, most probably, after conservation expert review and analysis, will have to be put in any IUCN Threatened category. Second plant species of this concern is the Balkan endemic *Sesleria wettsteinii* Dörfl. & Hayek, that was recorded in an exceedingly small and confined habitat of alpine grasslands with 25 mature individuals. Taking into account its very confined habitats in Kosovo (in Sharri Mts. in Luboten and Oshlak, and in Mt. Pashtrik), a critical review of its habitats and species overall situation, with potential inclusion into the Red list, with protection measures would have been highly advisable.

Life-form and Chorological spectrums

The life-form spectrum shows a clear predominance of hemicryptophytes (58.5%). The rather dry, calcareous substrate influences the life form spectrum of the flora, favouring hemicryptophytes. The phanerophytes are much less present (8.7%), due to, most probably, harsh environments for the development of these species. Additionally due to less plant diversity present on the belts of mixed as well as beech forests. The chorological spectrum analysis reveals a strong prevalence of Euro-Asiatic (19.4%) influence, well balanced with local Balkan floristic element species (14.1%), Orf. European floristic element (12.9%) and followed by Euri-Mediterranean (9.3%) and European (8.2%) floristic elements.

Conclusion

The present work contributes to the overall knowledge of the vascular flora of the Mt. Luboten, in Sharri Mountains. Our results further confirm that this mountainous area represents a hotspot for vascular plants because of the presence of many endemic and endangered plant taxa, and furthermore, due to the presence of two newly reported taxa for flora of Kosovo. This constitution of floristic richness fully supports the areas already declared status as a strict nature reserve within the Sharri National Park. Active management projects within this area would considerably assist the better preservation of wild plant taxa. This work highlights the floristic richness of some particular habitats and points out the need to provide their enhanced protection measures.

It is necessary to promote awareness in countries public administrations regarding the potential of floristic studies, as they represent a decisive and fundamental tool that supports the sustainability and proper managing of protected areas.

Annex I. List of recorded plant taxa on the Mt. Luboten, Sharri Mts., Kosovo.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
LYCOPODIACEAE										
1. <i>Huperzia selago</i> (L.) Schrank & Mart.	C	Subcosmop.	L-020	●	●	EN	H2.33			
SELAGINELLACEAE										
2. <i>Selaginella selaginoides</i> (L.) Schrank & Mart.	C	Arctic-Alp.	L-195		●	EN	D4.2			
OPHIOGLOSSACEAE										
3. <i>Botrychium lunaria</i> (L.) Sw.	G	Subcosmop.	L-001		●		E1.7			
EUQISETACEAE										
4. <i>Equisetum arvense</i> L.	G	Circumbor.	L-677	●			E3.4			LC
5. <i>Equisetum palustre</i> L.	G	Circumbor.	L-007	●			D2.2, E5.2			LC
DENNSTAEDIAACEAE										
6. <i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> (L.) Kuhn	G	Cosmopol.	L-004	●			G1.6C4, E5.3, E5.2, G1.A1			LC
PTERIDACEAE										
7. <i>Paragymnopteris marantae</i> (L.) K. H. Shing	H	Subtrop.	L-002				E1.2			NT
CYSTOPTERIDIACEAE										
8. <i>Cystopteris fragilis</i> (L.) Bernh.	H	Cosmopol.	L-006				E1.2			
ASPLENIACEAE										
9. <i>Asplenium adiantum-nigrum</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-676	●			F3.24311, G1.6922			
10. <i>Asplenium ceterach</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-008	●			E1.2, H3.2			LC
11. <i>Asplenium fissum</i> Willd.	H	Orof.SE Eur.	L-009				E4.14, E4.5, H3.216, H2.4, H2.3			
12. <i>Asplenium ruta-muraria</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-010				E1.22, E4.4, H2.4, F3.2			
13. <i>Asplenium trichomanes</i> L.	H	Cosmopol.	L-675	●			E1.22, F3.2			
14. <i>Asplenium viride</i> Huds.	H	Circumbor.	L-011				E4.4122, E5.5			LC
ATHYRIACEAE										
15. <i>Athyrium filix-femina</i> (L.) Roth	H	Subcosmop.	L-012				E4.1, D2.3, D2.38, D2.26, G3.1			
BLECHNACEAE										
16. <i>Blechnum spicant</i> (L.) Roth	H	Circumbor.	L-701	●			G1.6924			
DRYOPTERIDIACEAE										
17. <i>Dryopteris filix-mas</i> (L.) Schott.	G	Subcosmop.	L-021	●			G1.6C4, E5.2, G1.A1			
18. <i>Polystichum aculeatum</i> (L.) Roth	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-022	●			G1.6C4			

Annex. 1 - cont.

	FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
19.	<i>Polystichum lonchitis</i> (L.) Roth	G	Circumbor.	L-702	●	●		G4.6			
20.	<i>Polystichum setiferum</i> (Forssk.) Woynt.	G	Circumbor.	L-023				G1.A1, G4.6			
	POLYPODIACEAE										
21.	<i>Polypodium vulgare</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-674	●	●		F3.2, F3.2421			
	PINACEAE										
22.	<i>Abies alba</i> Mill.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-030	●			G1.6C4, G1.7C1, E5.2			
23.	<i>Picea abies</i> (L.) Karst	P	Euro-Siber.	L-031				G1.6C4, G3.162			
24.	<i>Pinus peuce</i> Griseb.	P	Balkan	L-032		●		H2.6B, E3.52, G3.1			End(B)
	CUPRESSACEAE										
25.	<i>Juniperus communis</i> L. subsp. <i>communis</i>	P	Circumbor.	L-034	●			F3.16, E4.34			
26.	<i>Juniperus communis</i> subsp. <i>nana</i> Syne.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-035	●	●		F2.231, E4.4, E4.34, H2.4			
	ARISTOLOCHIACEAE										
27.	<i>Aristolochia pallida</i> Willd.	G	Euri-Medit.	L-678	●			G1.6922, G1.7			
28.	<i>Asarum europaeum</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-195	●	●		G1.7, G3.1, G1.A1			
	ARACEAE										
29.	<i>Arum italicum</i> Mill.	G	Steno-Medit.	N/A	●			E1.22, F2.1, F2.231			
30.	<i>Arum maculatum</i> L.	G	Centro-Eur.	L-673	●			F2.231			
	NARTHECIACEAE										
31.	<i>Narthecium scardicum</i> Košanin	G	Balkan	L-005			NT	D2.28, D2.38, D2.26, D4.2			End(B)
	MELANTHIACEAE										
32.	<i>Veratrum lobelianum</i> Bernh.	G	Euro-Siber.	L-025				E4.4, E4.412			
33.	<i>Paris quadrifolia</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-679	●			G4.6			
	COLCHICACEAE										
34.	<i>Colchicum autumnale</i> L.	G	Centro-Eur.	L-003	●			E1.2, E1.22			
	DIOSCORIACEAE										
35.	<i>Dioscorea communis</i> (L.) Caddick & Wilkin	G	Euri-Medit.	L-672	●			F2.11, G1.6C4			
	LILIACEAE										
36.	<i>Erythronium dens-canis</i> L.	G	Orof.S.Eur.	L-013	●			G1.6922, G1.7C1, E5.5, E5.2			
37.	<i>Gagea lutea</i> (L.) Ker Gawl.	G	Euro-Siber.	L-014				F2, G4.6			
38.	<i>Lilium albanicum</i> Griseb.	G	Balkan	L-015	●	●	LC	F2.263, E4.116, E4.5			End(B)
39.	<i>Lilium martagon</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-016	●			F2.263, F2.3, F2.22, H2.3, G1.A1			
	ORCHIDACEAE										

Annex. 1 - cont.

	FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
40.	<i>Anacamptis laxiflora</i> (Lam.) R. M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M. W. Chase	G	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E5.5723	LC		
41.	<i>Anacamptis morio</i> (L.) R. M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M. W. Chase	G	Euro-Cauc.	L-680	●			E5.5723, E4.41731	NT		
42.	<i>Anacamptis palustris</i> (Jacq.) R. M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M. W. Chase	G	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			D2.282			
43.	<i>Anacamptis pyramidalis</i> (L.) Rich.	G	Euri-Medit.	L-671	●			E4.4, E4.4121	LC		
44.	<i>Dactylorhiza cordigera</i> (Fr.) Soó	G	Balkan	L-041				D2.2, D2.282	LC	End(B)	
45.	<i>Dactylorhiza maculata</i> (L.) Soó	G	Paleotemp.	L-042				G1.6C4, G4.6, D2.2	LC		
46.	<i>Dactylorhiza sambucina</i> (L.) Soó	G	Euro-Cauc.	L-043				D2.2, D2.282, G4.6	LC		
47.	<i>Dactylorhiza viridis</i> (L.) R. M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M. W. Chase	G	Circumbor.	N/A		●		G1.7, G1.6C4	LC		
48.	<i>Gymnadenia conopsea</i> (L.) R. Br.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-681	●			E4, E4.31	LC		
49.	<i>Gymnadenia friwaldii</i> Rchb.	G	Balkan	L-044			NT	E3.4, D2.3, D2.38, D2.26	LC		
50.	<i>Gymnadenia nigra</i> (L.) Rchb.f.	G	Euri-Medit.	L-045	●	●		E3.52, E4	LC		
51.	<i>Limodorum abortivum</i> (L.) Sw.	G	Medit.	N/A	●			F2.231, G1.6933	LC		
52.	<i>Neotinea maculata</i> (Desf.) Stearn	G	Medit.	L-046				F2.263, F2.231, D2.38, D2.26	LC		
53.	<i>Neotinea tridentata</i> (Scop.) R. M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M. W. Chase	G	Medit.	N/A	●			E4	LC		
54.	<i>Orchis purpurea</i> Huds.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-682	●			E3.4, E4.4, F2.22	LC		
55.	<i>Platanthera bifolia</i> (L.) Rich.	G	Paleotemp.	L-683	●			E3.52, E4, F2.231	LC		
	IRIDACEAE										
56.	<i>Crocus biflorus</i> subsp. <i>weldenii</i> (Hoppe & Fürnr.) K. Richt.	G	Medit.	L-196	●			E1.22, F2.23			
57.	<i>Crocus kosaninii</i> Pulevic	G	Submedit.	N/A	●		EN	G1.7		End(B)	
58.	<i>Crocus veluchensis</i> Herb.	G	Balkan	L-036	●	●		E4.3, E4.3411		End(B)	
59.	<i>Crocus vernus</i> (L.) Hill. subsp. <i>vernus</i>	G	Medit.	L-037				G1.6933, E4.3			
60.	<i>Iris graminea</i> L.	G	Euri-Medit.	L-178	●			G1.6933			
61.	<i>Iris pseudacorus</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			D2.2	LC		
62.	<i>Iris reichenbachii</i> Heuff.	G	Balkan	L-179	●			G4.6			
	AMARYLLIDACEAE										
63.	<i>Allium carinatum</i> L. subsp. <i>carinatum</i>	G	Europ.	L-684		●		E4.3, E4.39	LC		
64.	<i>Allium carinatum</i> subsp. <i>pulchellum</i> (G. Don) Bonnier & Layens	G	Europ.	L-017		●		E4.3, E4.39			
65.	<i>Allium ursinum</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-018				G1.6933, G3.1	LC		
66.	<i>Allium victorialis</i> L.	G	Circumbor.	N/A	●			F2.231	LC		

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
67. <i>Allium vineale</i> L.	G	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E5.2	LC		
68. <i>Galanthus nivalis</i> L.	G	Euro-Cauc.	L-019	●			G1.6933	NT		
ASPARAGACEAE										
69. <i>Muscari botryoides</i> (L.) Mill.	G	Euri-Medit.	L-470	●			G1.69322, E4			
70. <i>Muscari racemosum</i> Mill.	G	Submedit.	L-180	●			E4, E4.116			
71. <i>Asparagus tenuifolius</i> Lam.	C	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			G1.7C1, G4.6	LC		
72. <i>Convallaria majalis</i> L.	G	Euro-Siber.	L-038	●			G4.6, G1.6933			
73. <i>Ornithogalum comosum</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.55			
74. <i>Ornithogalum orthophyllum</i> subsp. <i>kochii</i> (Parl.) Maire & Weiller	G	Steno-Medit.	L-039	●			E4, E4.3411			
75. <i>Ornithogalum umbellatum</i> L.	G	Steno-Medit.	L-471	●			E4.3, E4.39			
76. <i>Polygonatum odoratum</i> (Mill.) Druce	G	Euro-Siber.	L-686	●			G1.6933			
77. <i>Polygonatum verticillatum</i> (L.) All.	G	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			G1.6933			
78. <i>Prospero autumnale</i> (L.) Speta	G	Steno-Medit.	N/A	●			E4.4			
79. <i>Scilla bifolia</i> L.	G	Euro-Cauc.	L-040	●			G1.6933			
TYPHACEAE										
80. <i>Typha latifolia</i> L.	G	Cosmopol.	L-472	●			D5.131	LC		
JUNCACEAE										
81. <i>Juncus articulatus</i> L.	G	Circumbor.	L-670	●			D2.2, E3.3	LC		
82. <i>Juncus conglomeratus</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-047	●			E3.52, E5.5721, D2.38, D2.26			
83. <i>Juncus effusus</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-048				D2.2, E5.2	LC		
84. <i>Juncus inflexus</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-714				E3.4, E3.5, D2.2			▼
85. <i>Juncus thomasi</i> Ten.	G	Europ.	L-049				D2.2, E5.5, E5.5721, D2.38, D2.26			
86. <i>Juncus trifidus</i> L.	G	Arctic-Alp.	L-473		●		E4.31, E4.14, E4.5			
87. <i>Luzula campestris</i> (L.) DC.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-050	●	●		E1.2, E1.7, E4.34			
88. <i>Luzula forsteri</i> (Sm.) DC.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-051	●			G1.6C4, G3.1			
89. <i>Luzula luzuloides</i> (Lam.) Dandy & Wilmott	H	Europ.	L-715				E4.3, E4.39, E4.312			
90. <i>Luzula multiflora</i> (Ehrh.) Lej. subsp. <i>multiflora</i>	H	Circumbor.	N/A		●		E1.2, E1.7			
91. <i>Luzula exspectata</i> Bacic & Jogan	H	Balkan	L-053				E5.5, E4.413A			
92. <i>Luzula spicata</i> (L.) D.C.	H	Orof.SE Eur.	L-052	●	●		E1.7, E4.3			
93. <i>Luzula sylvatica</i> (Huds.) Gaudin.	H	Orof.SE Eur.	L-054	●	●		F2.2, E4.41, E4.34			
CYPERACEAE										
94. <i>Blysmus compressus</i> (L.) Link	G	Euro-Siber.	L-055				D2.282, D4.1, D2.38, D2.26, D4.2			
95. <i>Carex atrata</i> L. subsp. <i>atrata</i>	H	Arctic-Alp.	L-474	●			E4.392			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
96. <i>Carex atrata</i> subsp. <i>aterrima</i> (Hoppe) Čelak.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-056	●			E4.392, E4.4121			
97. <i>Carex bulgarica</i> (Domin) Lazare	H	Balkan	L-067		●		E4.3, E4.39, E4.34			
98. <i>Carex caryophyllea</i> Latourr.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-057		●		E1.2, E1.22, E4.312			
99. <i>Carex curvula</i> All.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-058	●			E4.3, E4.3411			
100. <i>Carex distans</i> L.	H	Europ.	N/A	●			E3.4, E3.3			
101. <i>Carex echinata</i> Murray	H	Circumtemp.	L-060	●			D2.22, E5.2, D2.38, D2.26			
102. <i>Carex ferruginea</i> Scop.	G	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A	●			E4.392			
103. <i>Carex flava</i> L.	H	Circumtemp.	L-061	●			D2.2, D2.22, D2.3, D2.38, D2.26			
104. <i>Carex hirta</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E3.4			
105. <i>Carex kitaibeliana</i> Degen ex Bechere.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-063	●	●		E4.4, F2.1, H2.4			
106. <i>Carex leporina</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-064	●			E3.5, D2.2, D2.3, D2.38, D2.26			
107. <i>Carex nigra</i> (L.) Reichard	G	Subcosmop.	L-065				D2.22, D2.282, D2.38, D4.2			
108. <i>Carex ornithopoda</i> Willd.	H	Euro-Cauc.	N/A		●		E4.392			
109. <i>Carex pilulifera</i> L.	H	Europ.	N/A	●			E1.2			
110. <i>Carex pyrenaica</i> Wahlenb.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2			
111. <i>Carex rupestris</i> All.	H	Circumbor.	L-066		●		E4.4, E4.41			
112. <i>Carex sylvatica</i> Huds.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-068				G1.6C4, G1.7C1, E5.2, G1.A1			
113. <i>Eriophorum angustifolium</i> Honck.	G	Circumbor.	L-069				D2.22, D2.26, D2.282, D2.38	LC		
114. <i>Eriophorum latifolium</i> Hoppe.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-070				D2.2, D2.3, D2.38			
POACEAE										
115. <i>Aegilops triuncialis</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.7	LC		
116. <i>Agrostis canina</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-026	●			D2.2, D2.22, E5.2	LC		
117. <i>Agrostis capillaris</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	N/A	●	●		E1.2, E1.22, E3.3			
118. <i>Agrostis stolonifera</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-027				E1.55, E5.2, G1.1	LC		
119. <i>Alopecurus pratensis</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-475	●			D2.2, E3.3	LC		
120. <i>Alopecurus rendlei</i> Eig	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E3.4			
121. <i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-028	●	●		E4.41, E4.116, E5.2, E4.34, E3.3			
122. <i>Avenella flexuosa</i> (L.) Drejer	H	Subcosmop.	L-029	●	●		E1.73, E4.34, G3.1			
123. <i>Avenula pubescens</i> (Huds.) Dumort.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A		●		E4.1, E4.5			
124. <i>Bellardiochloa variegata</i> (Lam.) Kerguélen	H	Europ.	L-071	●	●		E4, E4.14, E4.34			

Annex. 1 - cont.

	FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
125.	<i>Brachypodium sylvaticum</i> (Huds.) P. Beauv.	H	Paleotemp.	L-669	●			D2.26, E1.2, G1.A1			
126.	<i>Briza media</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-223	●			E1.2, E1.73			
127.	<i>Bromopsis cappadocica</i> (Boiss. & Balansa) Holub subsp. <i>cappadocica</i>	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-072				E1.2, E1.22			■ ■
128.	<i>Bromopsis erecta</i> (Huds.) Fourr.	H	Paleotemp.	L-073	●	●		E1.22, E4.4, E4.41, H2.4			
129.	<i>Bromopsis riparia</i> (Rehmann) Holub	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2			
130.	<i>Bromus racemosus</i> L.	T	Europ.	L-074	●			E1.2, E5.2, E3.3			
131.	<i>Calamagrostis arundinacea</i> (L.) Roth	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-075	●	●		F2.2, E4.3, E4.39, E5.2			
132.	<i>Calamagrostis epigejos</i> (L.) Roth	H	Euro-Siber.	L-076				E1.7, E1.74			
133.	<i>Calamagrostis varia</i> (Schrad.) Host subsp. <i>varia</i>	H	Europ.	L-077				E5.5, E5.51			
134.	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	G	Cosmopol.	L-476	●			G1.6C4			
135.	<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2, E5.3			
136.	<i>Cynosurus echinatus</i> L.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E5.3			
137.	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-477	●			E1.2, E3.4, G1.A1			
138.	<i>Danthonia alpina</i> Vest	H	Europ.	L-668	●			E1.2, F2.231			
139.	<i>Danthonia decumbens</i> (L.) DC.	H	Europ.	L-685				F2.1, E4.1, E4.5			
140.	<i>Deschampsia cespitosa</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	H	Cosmopol.	L-078	●			D2.2, D2.22, E3.4, D2.38			
141.	<i>Festuca adamovicii</i> (St. Yves.) Markgr.-Dann.	H	Balkan	L-079		●		E4.41, E4.39, E4.4126, E1.112		End(B)	
142.	<i>Festuca bosniaca</i> Kumm. & Sendtn.	H	Medit.	L-080				E4.41			▼
143.	<i>Festuca halleri</i> subsp. <i>scardica</i> (Griseb.) Markgr.-Dann.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-478		●		E4.3, E4.31, E4.39, H2.4		End(B)	
144.	<i>Festuca heterophylla</i> Lam.	H	Euro-Cauc.	N/A	●			E1.7, F2.231, G1.A1	LC		
145.	<i>Festuca korabensis</i> (Markgr.-Dann.) Markgr.-Dann.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	N/A	●	●		E1.2			
146.	<i>Festuca koritnicensis</i> Hayek & J. Vetter	H	Balkan	L-081				E4.4, E4.41		End(B)	▼
147.	<i>Festuca panciana</i> (Hack.) K. Richt.	H	Balkan	L-082	●			E1.2, E1.22, E4.4, E4.34, H2.4			
148.	<i>Festuca rubra</i> L. subsp. <i>rubra</i>	H	Circumbor.	N/A		●		E1.2, E1.7, E3.5			
149.	<i>Festuca violacea</i> Gaudin	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-479	●	●		E4.3, E4.39, E4.392			
150.	<i>Helictochloa versicolor</i> (Vill.) Romero Zarco	H	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A	●	●		E4			
151.	<i>Holcus lanatus</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-480	●			E3.4			
152.	<i>Hordeum bulbosum</i> L.	H	Subtrop.	L-481	●			E5.2	LC		
153.	<i>Hordeum secalinum</i> Schreb.	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E3.3	LC		
154.	<i>Koeleria eriostachya</i> Panc.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-083	●	●		E1.2, E4.4, E4.41			
155.	<i>Koeleria lobata</i> (M. Bieb.) Roem. & Schult.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-084				E1.2, E1.22, E1.55, E4.34			
156.	<i>Lolium perenne</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-482	●			E1.2, E1.55, E3.3	LC		

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
157. <i>Melica ciliata</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-085	●			E1.2, E1.22, H2.6B			
158. <i>Melica uniflora</i> Retz.	H	Paleotemp.	L-483	●			F3.2421, G1.A1			
159. <i>Milium effusum</i> L.	G	Circumbor.	L-484	●			F2.231, G1.6C4, H3.2			
160. <i>Nardus stricta</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-086		●		F2.2, E4.31, E3.4, E4.34, D4.2			
161. <i>Ochlopoa annua</i> (L.) H. Scholz	T	Cosmopol.	N/A	●			E3.5			
162. <i>Patzkea paniculata</i> (L.) G. H. Loos	H	Medit.-Mont.	N/A		●		E4.39, E4.4			
163. <i>Phleum alpinum</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-087	●	●		E1.7, E4.4, E4.41			
164. <i>Phleum hirsutum</i> Honck.	G	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-088		●		E1.2, E4.3			
165. <i>Phleum montanum</i> Koch.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-089				E4, E4.4			
166. <i>Phleum pratense</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-485	●			E1.2, E3.4		LC	
167. <i>Poa alpina</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-090	●	●		E1.22, E4.31, H2.4		LC	
168. <i>Poa badensis</i> Haenke	H	Orof.Europ.	L-092	●			E1.2, E4.3, E4.39, H2.4			
169. <i>Poa bulbosa</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-093	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.112			
170. <i>Poa cenisia</i> All.	G	Europ.	N/A	●			E4.1, E4.116, E4.12			
171. <i>Poa chaixii</i> Vill.	H	Euro-Cauc.	N/A		●		E4, E4.4126			
172. <i>Poa media</i> Schur	H	Balkan.	N/A		●		E3.52, E3.4			
173. <i>Poa nemoralis</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	N/A	●			E1.2, F3.2421			
174. <i>Poa pratensis</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-486	●			E1.22, E3.4, E3.3		LC	
175. <i>Poa trivialis</i> subsp. <i>sylvicola</i> (Guss.) H. Lindb.	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E3.4			
176. <i>Schedonorus pratensis</i> (Huds.) P. Beauv.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.73			
177. <i>Sesleria autumnalis</i> (Scop.) F. W. Schultz	H	Orof.SE-Eur.	L-666	●			F3.2421			
178. <i>Sesleria coerulans</i> Friv.	H	Balkan.	N/A	●			E4.3, E4.39			
179. <i>Sesleria comosa</i> Velen.	H	Balkan.	L-487	●	●		E4.3, E4.31, E4.39		End(B)	
180. <i>Sesleria juncifolia</i> Suffren.	H	Anfriadiat.	L-095	●	●		E4.41, E4.4126, H2.4			
181. <i>Sesleria korabensis</i> (Kümmerle & Jáv.) Deyl	H	Balkan	N/A		●		E4.3925, E4.413A, E4.3		End(B)	
182. <i>Sesleria latifolia</i> (Adamović) Degen	H	Ilyrian-Apen.	L-096	●			H2.6B, E4.3925, H2.4, E1.112			
183. <i>Sesleria wettsteinii</i> Dörf & Hayek.	H	Balkan	L-098		●		E4.41, E4.412		End(B)	CONS. +
RANUNCULACEAE										
184. <i>Actaea spicata</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-201	●			G1.6C4			
185. <i>Adonis flammea</i> Jacq.	T	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			G1.7			
186. <i>Anemonastrum narcissiflorum</i> (L.) Holub	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-202	●	●		E4.3, E4.39, E4.392			
187. <i>Anemone nemorosa</i> L.	G	Circumbor.	L-203	●	●		G1.6C4, E5.2, G3.1			
188. <i>Anemone ranunculoides</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-204	●			G1.6C4			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
189. <i>Caltha palustris</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-205	●			D4.1, E3.4, D2.3, D2.38, D2.26	LC		
190. <i>Clematis vitalba</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-493	●			F3.2421, G1.A1			
191. <i>Consolida regalis</i> Gray	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-488	●			E3.3			
192. <i>Ficaria verna</i> Huds.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-206	●			G1.6933, G1.A1			
193. <i>Helleborus odoros</i> Waldst. & Kit. ex Willd.	G	Orof.SE-Eur.	L-207	●			E1.2, F3.2421, G1.A1			
194. <i>Isopyrum thalictroides</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-208	●			G1.7C1			
195. <i>Nigella arvensis</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-687	●			E1.2			
196. <i>Ranunculus acris</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-489	●			E4.4125, E3.3			
197. <i>Ranunculus arvensis</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-490	●			G3.17			
198. <i>Ranunculus breyninus</i> Crantz	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-209				E3.5			
199. <i>Ranunculus bulbosus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.22			
200. <i>Ranunculus crenatus</i> Waldst. & Kit.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-688	●			E4.1, E4.116, E4.5			
201. <i>Ranunculus fontanus</i> C. Presl	T	Medit.-Mont.	L-725				D2.2	DD		CONS. +
202. <i>Ranunculus millefoliatus</i> Vahl	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			G1.7			
203. <i>Ranunculus montanus</i> Willd.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-210	●	●		F2.2, G1.7, E1.2, D2.38, D2.26			
204. <i>Ranunculus platanifolius</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-212	●			G1.6C4, E3.5			
205. <i>Ranunculus polyanthemus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E3.5, E4			
206. <i>Ranunculus repens</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-492	●			E3.5, E4.4121, E3.3	LC		
207. <i>Ranunculus sardous</i> Crantz	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-494	●			E3.3, E3.4			
208. <i>Thalictrum aquilegifolium</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-213	●	●		E1.2, F3.2421, G1.7			
209. <i>Thalictrum minus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-214				E1.2, E1.22, H2.3			
210. <i>Trollius europaeus</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-215	●		LC	E3.5, E4.1, E4.5			
PAPAVERACEAE										
211. <i>Chelidonium majus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-495	●			G1.A1			
212. <i>Corydalis cava</i> (L.) Schweigg. & Körte	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-105	●			G1.6C4, G1.A1			
213. <i>Corydalis solida</i> (L.) Clairv.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-106	●			G1.6C4, G1.6924, G1.A1			
214. <i>Papaver rhoeas</i> L.	T	Paleotemp.	L-496	●			G1.7			
215. <i>Pseudofumaria alba</i> (Mill.) Lidén subsp. <i>alba</i>	H	Anfriadiat.	L-107				H2.6, H2.6B			
CRASSULACEAE										
216. <i>Jovibarba heuffelii</i> (Schott) Á. Löve & D. Löve	C	Balkan	L-114	●	●	LC	E1.22, E4.4			
217. <i>Sedum acre</i> L.	C	Euro-Siber.	L-115	●			E1.2, E4.41, E4.4121, E4.34			
218. <i>Sedum album</i> L.	C	Euro-Asiat.	L-116				E1.2, E1.22, H2.4			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
219. <i>Sedum annuum</i> L.	T	Arctic-Alp.	L-665	●	●		E1.112, H3.2			
220. <i>Sedum atratum</i> L.	T	Europ.	L-117		●		E1.2, E1.22, H3.216			
221. <i>Sedum cepaea</i> L.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			H3.216			
222. <i>Sedum grisebachii</i> subsp. <i>flexuosum</i> (Wettst.) Greut. & Burd.	H	Balkan.	L-689	●	●		H3.1, H3.152			
223. <i>Sedum hispanicum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-118	●	●		G1.7, G1.6924			
224. <i>Sedum magellense</i> Ten.	C	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			G1.6C4, H2.6			
225. <i>Sedum maximum</i> (L.) Holub.	H	Euro-Siber.	N/A	●			F3.2421			
226. <i>Sedum ochroleucum</i> Chaix.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-119	●	●		E1.2, E1.22, F3.2421, H2.4			
227. <i>Sempervivum erythraeum</i> Velen.	C	Balkan	N/A		●		E1.112			
228. <i>Sempervivum macedonicum</i> Praeger	C	Balkan	L-120			LC	E1.7, E1.112			End(B)
SAXIFRAGACEAE										
229. <i>Chrysosplenium alternifolium</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	N/A	●			G1.6933			
230. <i>Saxifraga adscendens</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-121		●		F2.3, F2.231, H2.33, H2.4			
231. <i>Saxifraga aizoides</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-122		●		D4.1, E4.4, E4.41, D2.38, D2.26			
232. <i>Saxifraga bulbifera</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			G1.7			
233. <i>Saxifraga exarata</i> Vill.	H	Orof.SE-Eur.	N/A	●			H2.6			
234. <i>Saxifraga marginata</i> Sternb.	C	Orof.SE-Eur.	L-124				H3.2, H2.6, H2.4			
235. <i>Saxifraga moschata</i> Wulfen.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-125	●	●		H3.1, H3.152, E1.112			
236. <i>Saxifraga paniculata</i> Mill.	H	Arctic-Alp.	L-126	●			G1.6922, H3.2, H3.152, H2.4			
237. <i>Saxifraga rotundifolia</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-127	●			D4.1, H2.33, F3.24311			
238. <i>Saxifraga scardica</i> Griseb.	C	Balkan	L-128	●	●	LC	H2.6, H2.6B, H2.4			End(B)
239. <i>Saxifraga sempervivum</i> Koch.	C	Balkan	L-129	●	●	LC	E4.41, E4.412, F2.1, H2.4, E1.112			
240. <i>Saxifraga taygetea</i> Boiss. & Heldr.	H	Balkan	L-130	●		EN	H3.1, H3.152			End(B)
241. <i>Saxifraga tridactylites</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-131				H3.2, H3.216			
VITACEAE										
242. <i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-497	●			G1.6C4, G1.6933	LC		
PARNASSIACEAE										
243. <i>Parnassia palustris</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-033				D2.2, D2.22, D2.3, D2.38, D2.26			
CELASTRACEAE										
244. <i>Euonymus europaeus</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-500	●			G1.7, F3.2, G3.1, G1.A1			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
245. <i>Euonymus verrucosus</i> Scop.	P	Europ.	L-501	●			G1.6933, F3.2421, G1.6C4, G1.A1			
OXALIDACEAE										
246. <i>Oxalis acetosella</i> L.	C	Circumbor.	L-099	●			G1.6933, G1.7, E5.2, G3.1			
CLUSIACEAE										
247. <i>Hypericum barbatum</i> Jacq.	H	Europ.	L-498	●			E1.2, E1.55, E4.4			
248. <i>Hypericum maculatum</i> Crantz	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-499	●	●		E1.7, E4.3, E4.31, E4.312			
249. <i>Hypericum montanum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-101				E4.3, E4.39, E4.392, E5.2			
250. <i>Hypericum perforatum</i> subsp. <i>latifolium</i> (Gaudin) A. Frohl.	H	Paleotemp.	L-102	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.7, E5.2, E4.34			
251. <i>Hypericum richeri</i> subsp. <i>grisebachii</i> (Boiss.) Nyman	H	Europ.	L-103	●	●		E4.3, E4.31, E4.312 , E4.39			
SALICACEAE										
252. <i>Populus alba</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-502	●			G1.7			
253. <i>Populus tremula</i>	P	Circumtemp.	L-132	●			F3.2421, G1.6922, G1.6C4, E5.2			
254. <i>Salix alba</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-503	●			F3.2421, G1.1			
255. <i>Salix caprea</i> L.	P	Euro-Siber.	L-133				G1.6933, G3.12, G4.6, E5.2			
256. <i>Salix reticulata</i> L.	C	Circumbor.	L-134	●		LC	E1.7, E4.41, E4.4125, F2.12			
257. <i>Salix retusa</i> L.	C	Orof.Europ.	L-135	●	●		E4.4, E4.412, F2.1, F2.12			
VIOLACEAE										
258. <i>Viola elegantula</i> Schott.	H	Ballkan	L-109			LC	E1.73, E4.3922, E4.4122		End(B)	
259. <i>Viola grisebachiana</i> Vis.	H	Ballkan	L-111			EN	H2.6, H2.6B		End(B)	
260. <i>Viola jordanii</i> Hanry	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-690	●			G1.6C4			
261. <i>Viola kitaibeliana</i> Schult.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.22			
262. <i>Viola odorata</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-112	●			G1.7, G1.6C4, G1.A1			
263. <i>Viola orphanidis</i> Boiss.	H	Ballkan	L-110	●		LC	E5.5721, E4.413A, G3.12		End(B)	
264. <i>Viola reichenbachiana</i> Boreau	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			G1.6C4			
265. <i>Viola schariensis</i> Erben	H	Ballkan	L-113				E4.41, E4.4122		End(B)	▼
266. <i>Viola tricolor</i> L. subsp. <i>tricolor</i>	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-104	●			E1.74, F2.23, G1.7			

Annex. 1 - cont.

	FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
267.	<i>Viola tricolor</i> subsp. <i>macedonica</i> (Boiss. & Heldr.) A. F. W. Schmidt LINACEAE	T	Balkan	L-504		●		E1.7		End(B)	
268.	<i>Linum capitatum</i> Kit. ex Schult.	C	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-099	●	●		E4.3, E4.31, E4.39, E4.34		End(B)	
269.	<i>Linum catharticum</i> L.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.73			
270.	<i>Linum flavum</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-505	●		LC	E1.2, E1.22			
271.	<i>Linum hologynum</i> Rchb.	H	Balkan	N/A	●			E1.2, E5.4			
272.	<i>Linum perenne</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-663	●			E1.2, E1.74			
273.	<i>Linum tenuifolium</i> L. EUPHORBIACEAE	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-664	●			E1.2, E4.392			
274.	<i>Euphorbia amygdaloides</i> L.	C	Euro-Cauc.	L-136	●			E4.412, F2.23 E5.2, G3.1, G1.A1			
275.	<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i> L.	H	Centro-Eur.	L-137	●			E1.22, E1.7			
276.	<i>Euphorbia epithymoides</i> L.	H	Europ.	N/A	●			G1.7C1			
277.	<i>Euphorbia glabriflora</i> Vis.	C	Balkan	L-662	●			E1.2, F3.2421		End(B)	
278.	<i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i> L.	T	Cosmopol.	L-506	●			E1.2			
279.	<i>Euphorbia myrsinites</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-507	●			E1.2, G1.7			
280.	<i>Mercurialis perennis</i> L. FABACEAE	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-508	●			E4.4, G1.6C4, G1.A1			
281.	<i>Anthyllis aurea</i> Welden.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-253				E1.22, E4.4, E4.4125		End(B)	
282.	<i>Anthyllis montana</i> L.	C	Medit.	L-509	●			E4.4126, E4.41731, E1.112			
283.	<i>Anthyllis vulneraria</i> subsp. <i>alpestris</i> (Schult.) Asch. & Graebn.	H	Balkan	L-255		●		E4.41731			
284.	<i>Astragalus glycyphyllos</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	N/A	●			F3.2421, G1.7			
285.	<i>Astragalus onobrychis</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-510	●			E1.112			
286.	<i>Colutea arborescens</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-511	●			F3.2421, G1.7			
287.	<i>Cytisus albus</i> Hacq.	C	Balkan	L-258	●	●		F2.2, F3.2421			
288.	<i>Cytisus hirsutus</i> L.	C	Euro-Siber.	L-256	●			F2.3, F2.32			
289.	<i>Cytisus procumbens</i> (Willd.) Spreng.	C	Balkan	L-257	●			F2.2, F2.23			
290.	<i>Genista depressa</i> M. Bieb.	C	Balkan	L-259				E1.2, E1.7			▼
291.	<i>Genista sagittalis</i> L.	C	Europ.	L-512	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.7			
292.	<i>Genista tinctoria</i> L.	C	Euro-Siber.	L-260	●			E1.2, G1.6C4			
293.	<i>Hippocrepis comosa</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-100	●			E1.2, E4.392			
294.	<i>Hippocrepis glauca</i> Ten.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-221		●		E1.2			
295.	<i>Lathyrus aphaca</i> L.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●	●		G1.7, G1.A1			
296.	<i>Lathyrus latifolius</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-123	●			E1.7, E1.74	LC		

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
297. <i>Lathyrus niger</i> (L.) Bernh.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-513	●			G1.6924, G1.7			
298. <i>Lathyrus pratensis</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.73			
299. <i>Lathyrus tuberosus</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-661	●			E3.4	LC		
300. <i>Lembotropis nigricans</i> (L.) Griseb.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A	●			F3.242, G1.7			
301. <i>Lotus corniculatus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-222	●	●		E1.22, E1.7, E5.2, E3.3	LC		
302. <i>Lotus tenuis</i> Willd.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E3.4			
303. <i>Medicago prostrata</i> Jacq.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-514	●			E1.2, E1.7, E1.22	LC	End(B)	
304. <i>Onobrychis montana</i> subsp. <i>scardica</i> Griseb.	H	Balkan	L-224	●	●		E4.4, E4.41, E4.412, E1.112		End(B)	
305. <i>Ononis spinosa</i> L.	C	Euri-Medit.	L-660	●			E3.4			
306. <i>Oxytropis dinarica</i> (Murb.) Wettst.	H	Balkan	L-703		●		E4.4		End(B)	
307. <i>Oxytropis halleri</i> subsp. <i>korabensis</i> (Küm. & Jáv.) Chr. & Ch.	H	Balkan	L-227		●		E4.4, E4.412		End(B)	
308. <i>Oxytropis jacquinii</i> Bunge	C	Endem.Alp.	L-704		●		E4.4, E4.42			
309. <i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	P	N. Amer.	L-515	●			G1.7			
310. <i>Trifolium alpestre</i> L.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-228	●	●		E1.2, E1.22, E1.73, E4.31	LC		
311. <i>Trifolium arvense</i> L.	T	Paleotemp.	L-659	●			E1.2, E1.22	LC		
312. <i>Trifolium badium</i> Schreb.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-229	●			D2.3, D2.38			
313. <i>Trifolium campestre</i> Schreb.	T	Paleotemp.	L-230	●			E1.2, E4.116, E4.391, E5.2, E4.34			
314. <i>Trifolium echinatum</i> M. Bieb.	T	Euri-Medit.	L-516	●			E1.22, G1.7			
315. <i>Trifolium fragiferum</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	N/A	●			E3.4, E3.3			
316. <i>Trifolium hybridum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-231				E3.4, E3.5	LC		
317. <i>Trifolium incarnatum</i> L.	T	Euri-Medit.	L-517	●			E1.2, E1.22	LC		
318. <i>Trifolium medium</i> subsp. <i>balcanicum</i> Velen	G	Balkan	L-252	●			F2.32, E5.2		End(B)	
319. <i>Trifolium nigrescens</i> Viv.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E4.42	LC		
320. <i>Trifolium noricum</i> Wulf.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-233	●			E4.4, E4.41, E4.412			
321. <i>Trifolium patens</i> Schreb.	T	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.22, E3.4			
322. <i>Trifolium pignantii</i> Fauché & Chaub.	G	Balkan	L-234	●			F3.2421, G1.7, G1.A1		End(B)	
323. <i>Trifolium pratense</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-235	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.7, E1.73, E5.2	LC		
324. <i>Trifolium repens</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-136	●	●		E4.4125, E5.5721, E1.22, D2.38	LC		
325. <i>Trifolium resupinatum</i> L.	T	Paleotemp.	L-518	●			E3.4, E3.3	LC		
326. <i>Trifolium velenovskyi</i> Vandas	H	Balkan	L-137	●			E1.7, E1.73, E1.74		End(B)	
327. <i>Trifolium wettsteinii</i> Dörf. & Hayek	C	Balkan	L-519	●		EN	E1.22, E4.4, E4.412		End(B)	

POLYGALACEAE

Annex. 1 - cont.

	FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
328.	<i>Polygala alpestris</i> Reichenb.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-141				E4.4125			
329.	<i>Polygala comosa</i> Schkuhr.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-142	●	●		E1.2, E1.22			
330.	<i>Polygala major</i> Jacq.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-143	●			E1.2, E1.22, E4.41			
331.	<i>Polygala vulgaris</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-144	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.7			
ROSACEAE											
332.	<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i> L.	H	Subcosmop.	L-521	●			E1.2, E1.7, E4.3925			
333.	<i>Alchemilla connivens</i> Buser	H	Europ.	L-251	●			E4.116, E4.5			
334.	<i>Alchemilla flabellata</i> Buser	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-520	●	●		E4.31, E4.3925, E1.92			
335.	<i>Alchemilla glaucescens</i> Wallr.	H	Europ.	L-303				F2.231, E5.5721, D2.38, E4.34			
336.	<i>Alchemilla velebitica</i> Borb s ex Janch.	H	Balkan	L-305	●			H2.6B, H2.6B3			
337.	<i>Alchemilla viridiflora</i> Rothm.	H	Balkan	L-306				D2.2, E5.5721			End(B)
338.	<i>Aremonia agrimonoides</i> (L.) DC.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-522	●	●		G1.6933, G3.1			
339.	<i>Aruncus dioicus</i> (Walter) Fernald	H	Circumbor.	L-307	●			G1.6933, E4.412			
340.	<i>Cotoneaster integerrimus</i> Medik.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-691	●			E1.2, E1.22, E4.4, E4.4122			
341.	<i>Cotoneaster nebrodensis</i> (Guss.) C. Koch.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-308				H3.152			
342.	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i> Jacq.	P	Paleotemp.	L-523	●			E1.2, G1.7, G1.A1			
343.	<i>Crataegus pentagyna</i> Willd.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-692	●			G3.12, F3.2421			
344.	<i>Dryas octopetala</i> L.	C	Steno-Medit.	L-309	●	●		E4.4, E4.41, H2.6, H3.1, H2.4			
345.	<i>Filipendula ulmaria</i> (L.) Maxim.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-310				E5.5, E5.51, E4.413A			
346.	<i>Filipendula vulgaris</i> Moench	H	Euro-Siber.	L-524	●			E1.73			
347.	<i>Fragaria vesca</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-311	●			E1.22, E4.392, E5.2, G3.1, G1.A1		LC	
348.	<i>Geum coccineum</i> Sibth. et.Sm.	H	Balkan	L-312	●	●		E5.51, E5.5721, D2.38, D2.26			
349.	<i>Geum montanum</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-313	●	●		E4.3, E4.31, E4.312, E1.92, E4.34			
350.	<i>Geum urbanum</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-314	●			E5.4, E5.5721, E5.2, G1.A1			
351.	<i>Malus sylvestris</i> (L.) Mill.	P	Europ.	L-525	●			G1.6933		DD	
352.	<i>Potentilla aurea</i> subsp. <i>chrysocraspeda</i> (Lehm.) Nyman	H	Balkan	L-316	●	●		E4.39			
353.	<i>Potentilla doerfleri</i> Wettst.	H	Balkan	L-178			EN	H3.15, H3.152			End(B)
354.	<i>Potentilla hirta</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-693	●			E1.22, E1.7			
355.	<i>Potentilla inclinata</i> Vill.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.22			
356.	<i>Potentilla recta</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-658	●			E1.2, F3.2421, G1.7			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
357. <i>Potentilla reptans</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-526	●			D4.1, E3.4, E3.3			
358. <i>Potentilla tommasiniana</i> F. W. Schultz	H	Pontic	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.22, G1.7C1			
359. <i>Prunus avium</i> (L.) L.	P	Pontic	L-317	●			G1.6C4, G1.7C1, G4.6, G1.A1	LC		
360. <i>Prunus spinosa</i> L.	P	Euro-Cauc.	L-527	●			F3.242, G1.A1	LC		
361. <i>Pyrus communis</i> subsp. <i>pyraster</i> (L.) Ehrh.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-528	●			F3.2421, G1.A1	LC		
362. <i>Rosa arvensis</i> Huds.	P	Euri-Medit.	L-529	●			G1.7, G1.A1			
363. <i>Rosa canina</i> L.	P	Paleotemp.	L-530	●			E1.2, F3.2421			
364. <i>Rosa gallica</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-657	●			G1.7			
365. <i>Rosa glauca</i> Pourret.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-318				G1.7, E4.34			
366. <i>Rosa micrantha</i> Sm.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-319	●			E4.41, E5.2			
367. <i>Rosa pendulina</i> L.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-320		●		G1.A1, G1.6C4, G1.7, E5.3			
368. <i>Rosa pulverulenta</i> M. Bieb.	P	Medit.-Mont.	L-321				D2.282			
369. <i>Rosa villosa</i> L.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-322				F2.22			
370. <i>Rubus canescens</i> DC.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-323				G1.7			
371. <i>Rubus idaeus</i> L.	P	Circumbor.	L-324	●	●		G1.7, E1.92, E4.41, H2.6, G3.1			
372. <i>Sanguisorba minor</i> Scop.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-531	●			E1.2, E1.22			
373. <i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-532	●			D2.3, D2.38			
374. <i>Sorbus aria</i> (L.) Crantz	P	Euri-Medit.	L-533	●			E5.5, F3.2421			
375. <i>Sorbus aucuparia</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-534	●			G1.6933, G3.1			
376. <i>Sorbus austriaca</i> (Beck) Prain & al.	P	Europ.	L-326				F2.1, F2.2			
377. <i>Sorbus chamaemespilus</i> (L.) Crantz	P	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A		●		F2.32, F2.231			
378. <i>Sorbus domestica</i> L.	P	Euri-Medit.	L-535	●			G1.7			
379. <i>Sorbus torminalis</i> (L.) Crantz	P	Paleotemp.	L-536	●			G1.7, G1.7C1, G1.A1			
380. <i>Waldsteinia geoides</i> Willd.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-537	●			G1.7, G4.6			
MORACEAE										
381. <i>Morus alba</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-694	●			G1.1			
RHAMNACEAE										
382. <i>Rhamnus alpina</i> subsp. <i>fallax</i> (Boiss.) M. & P.	P	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-160		●		E4.412, G1.6933			
ULMACEAE										
383. <i>Ulmus glabra</i> Huds.	P	Euro-Cauc.	L-538	●			G1.6933, G1.7, G1.A1			
URTICACEAE										
384. <i>Urtica dioica</i> L.	H	Subcosmop.	L-150	●	●		E5.5721, E4.41731, E5.2, G1.1	LC		
385. <i>Urtica urens</i> L.	T	Subcosmop.	N/A	●			G1.7			

Annex. 1 - cont.

	FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
	GERANIACEAE										
386.	<i>Erodium cicutarium</i> (L.) L'Hér.	T	Subcosmop.	L-539	●			G1.7, E1.92			
387.	<i>Geranium lucidum</i> L.	T	Euri-Medit.	L-656	●			H2.6, H2.6B, H2.6B3			
388.	<i>Geranium macrorrhizum</i> L.	G	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-145	●	●		E1.2, E1.22, F2.2, F2.23			
389.	<i>Geranium molle</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.22			
390.	<i>Geranium robertianum</i> L.	T	Subcosmop.	L-146	●			E5.43, G1.6933, E5.2, G1.A1			
391.	<i>Geranium subcaulescens</i> DC.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-179			LC	E4.3, E4.31, E4.39, F2.2			
392.	<i>Geranium sylvaticum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-147	●	●		F2.32, G1.6933			
	FAGACEAE										
393.	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> L.	P	Centro-Eur.	L-138	●			G1.6933, G1.6C4, E5.2, G3.1			
394.	<i>Quercus cerris</i> L.	P	Euri-Medit.	L-540	●			G1.7, F3.2421, G1.69, G1.A1			
395.	<i>Quercus frainetto</i> Ten.	P	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-541	●			G1.7, G1.A1			
396.	<i>Quercus petraea</i> (Matt.) Liebl.	P	Europ.	L-542	●			G1.6933, F3.242, G1.A1			
397.	<i>Quercus pubescens</i> Willd.	P	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-543	●			G1.7			
	BETULACEAE										
398.	<i>Betula pendula</i> Roth.	P	Euro-Siber.	L-151	●			G1.7, G4.6, E5.2			
	LYTHRACEAE										
399.	<i>Lythrum salicaria</i> L.	H	Subcosmop.	L-544	●			D4.1, D2.3, D5.131	LC		
	ONAGRACEAE										
400.	<i>Circaea lutetiana</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-190	●			G1.1, E5.43, E5.2, G1.A1			
401.	<i>Epilobium angustifolium</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-191				F2.231, F2.2, E1.92			
402.	<i>Epilobium montanum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-192	●			G1.6933, E4.3, E5.2, D2.38			
	SAPINDACEAE										
403.	<i>Acer campestre</i> L.	P	Euro-Cauc.	L-197	●			F2.2, F2.23, F2.263, E5.2, G1.A1			
404.	<i>Acer heldreichii</i> Orph. ex Boiss.	P	Balkan	L-198			EN	G1.6933		End(B)	▼
405.	<i>Acer hyrcanum</i> subsp. <i>intermedium</i> (Pančić) Bornm.	P	Balkan	N/A	●			F3.2421		End(B)	
406.	<i>Acer obtusatum</i> Willd.	P	Euri-Medit.	L-545	●			F3.242, G1.6924			
407.	<i>Acer platanoides</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-199	●			F3.2421, G1.6933, E5.2, G1.A1			
408.	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i> L.	P	Europ.	L-200	●			F2.2, F2.23, G1.A1, F3.2421, G3.1			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
409. <i>Acer tataricum</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-546	●			G4.6, E5.43, G1.A1			
THYMELACEAE										
410. <i>Daphne laureola</i> L.	P	Euri-Medit.	L-547	●			G1.6933			
411. <i>Daphne mezereum</i> L.	P	Euro-Siber.	L-149	●	●		F2.2, E4.41, E4.412, G3.1			
412. <i>Daphne oleoides</i> Schreb.	C	Medit.-Mont.	L-148				H2.6, H2.4, E4.4			
CORYLACEAE										
413. <i>Carpinus betulus</i> L.	P	Euro-Cauc.	L-548	●			F3.2421, G1.A1			
414. <i>Carpinus orientalis</i> Mill.	P	Pontic	L-549	●			F3.2421, G1.7, G1.A1			
415. <i>Corylus avellana</i> L.	P	Euro-Cauc.	L-550	●			G1.7			
416. <i>Corylus colurna</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-551	●			G1.6924			
417. <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> Scop.	P	Circumbor.	L-153	●			G1.6924, G1.7C1			
CISTACEAE										
418. <i>Helianthemum alpestre</i> (Jacq.) DC.	C	Euri-Medit.	L-705		●		E4.4, E4.41			
419. <i>Helianthemum canum</i> (L.) Baumg.	C	Euro-Cauc.	L-181	●	●		E1.22, E4.4122, E4.4126, H2.4			
420. <i>Helianthemum nummularium</i> (L.) Mill. subsp. <i>nummularium</i>	C	Euro-Cauc.	L-182	●	●		E1.2, E1.22, E1.73, E1.92			
421. <i>Helianthemum nummularium</i> subsp. <i>grandiflorum</i> (Scop.) Schinz & Thell.	C	Orof.S.Eur.	L-183				E3.4, E1.2, E4.3			
MALVACEAE										
422. <i>Alcea biennis</i> Winterl	H	Medit.-Mont.	N/A	●			I1.3			
423. <i>Malva sylvestris</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-552	●			I1.3			
424. <i>Tilia platyphyllos</i> Scop.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-553	●			G1.7			
425. <i>Tilia tomentosa</i> Moench	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-139	●			G1.7, E5.2, G1.A1			
RESEDACEAE										
426. <i>Reseda lutea</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-554	●			E1.2			
BRASSICACEAE										
427. <i>Aethionema saxatile</i> (L.) W. T. Aiton	C	Medit.-Mont.	L-161	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.7			
428. <i>Alyssum montanum</i> L.	C	Centro-Eur.	L-162	●			E1.2, E4.4, E4.41			
429. <i>Alyssum scardicum</i> Wettst.	C	Balkan	L-555		●		E4.4, E4.41, E4.412		End(B)	
430. <i>Arabis alpina</i> subsp. <i>caucasica</i> (Willd.) Briq.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-164	●	●		E4.1, E4.5, H2.4			
431. <i>Arabis ciliata</i> Clairv.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-165				E4.4, E4.41, E1.73			▼
432. <i>Arabis hirsuta</i> (L.) Scop.	H	Europ.	L-166				E1.2, F3.2421			▼
433. <i>Arabis serpyllifolia</i> Vill.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-188				H2.4			▼
434. <i>Aubrieta columnae</i> subsp. <i>croatica</i> (Schott, Nyman, Kotschy)Mattf.	C	Balkan	L-167	●		CR	H3.216, H3.2A13, H2.4, E1.112			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
435. <i>Barbarea balcana</i> Pančić	H	Balkan	L-180			NT	E5.57	LC	End(B)	
436. <i>Barbarea vulgaris</i> R. Br.	H	Cosmopol.	L-168				G1.7, D2.26	LC		
437. <i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> (L.) Medik.	H	Cosmopol.	L-556	●			G1.7, E5.4			
438. <i>Cardamine bulbifera</i> (L.) Crantz.	G	Centro-Eur.	L-169	●			G1.6933, G1.A1			
439. <i>Cardamine carnosa</i> Waldst. et Kit.	H	Balkan	L-170				H3.2A13, D2.38, D2.26, H2.3		End(B)	▼
440. <i>Cardamine enneaphyllos</i> (L.) Crantz	G	Orof.SE-Eur.	L-171	●			G1.6933			
441. <i>Cardamine flexuosa</i> With.	H	Circumbor.	L-172				G1.6933, E5.4, E5.2			
442. <i>Cardamine glauca</i> DC. subsp. <i>glauca</i>	T	Balkan	L-707				D4.1, H2.4			
443. <i>Cardamine hirsuta</i> L.	T	Medit.-Mont.	L-706				E5.4			
444. <i>Cardamine impatiens</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-708				E5.4, G1.7			
445. <i>Cardamine pratensis</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-174	●			D2.2, G1.69322	LC		
446. <i>Draba aizoides</i> L.	H	Orof.C.Eur.	L-695		●		E4.4, E4.41, E4.4126			
447. <i>Draba doerfleri</i> Wettst.	C	Balkan	L-557				H3.152		End(B)	
448. <i>Draba praecox</i> Steven	T	Steno-Medit.	L-655		●		E4.392, E1.7			
449. <i>Draba scardica</i> (Griseb.) Degen & Dörfler	H	Balkan	L-175	●			E4.41, H3.2, H2.4			
450. <i>Draba verna</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-176	●			E3.4, E3.5			
451. <i>Erysimum carnolicum</i> Dolliner	H	Balkan	N/A	●			E1.2			
452. <i>Erysimum comatum</i> Pančić	H	Balkan	L-154				E4.41, E4.412, E4.4126			▼
453. <i>Erysimum diffusum</i> Ehrh.	H	Europ.	N/A	●			E1.2, H2.6			
454. <i>Iberis sempervirens</i> L.	C	Medit.	L-155		●	LC	E4.4, E4.41, E4.4125			
455. <i>Lepidium draba</i> L.	G	Cosmopol.	L-654	●			G1.7			
456. <i>Noccaea bellidifolia</i> (Griseb.) F. K. Mey.	H	Balkan	L-156	●	●		E4.41, E4.412, H2.6, E4.34		End(B)	
457. <i>Noccaea goesingensis</i> (Halácsy) F. K. Mey.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			G4.6			
458. <i>Noccaea ochroleuca</i> (Boiss. & Heldr.) F. K. Mey.	H	Balkan	L-558				G1.6933, E1.7, E1.73, E4.31			
459. <i>Noccaea perfoliata</i> (L.) Al-Shehbaz	T	Paleotemp.	N/A	●			F3.2421			
460. <i>Noccaea praecox</i> (Wulfen) F. K. Mey.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-157				E1.2, E4.31			
461. <i>Odontarrhena markgrafii</i> (O. E. Schulz) Španiel & al.	C	Balkan	N/A	●			E1.2, F3.242			
462. <i>Odontarrhena muralis</i> (Waldst. & Kit.) Endl.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2			
463. <i>Phyllolepidium rupestre</i> (Ten.) Trinajstić	C	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-158		●	EN	E4.41731			
464. <i>Pseudoturritis turrita</i> (L.) Al-Shehbaz	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-653	●			F3.242			
465. <i>Rorippa pyrenaica</i> (All.) Rchb.	H	Europ.	N/A	●			E5.3	LC		
466. <i>Rorippa sylvestris</i> (L.) Besser	H	Europ.	L-559	●			D5.131	LC		
467. <i>Thlaspi arvense</i> L.	T	Cosmopol.	L-560	●			E5.4			
468. <i>Turritis glabra</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-159				E1.2, E1.22, G1.7			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
SANTALACEAE										
469. <i>Thesium alpinum</i> L.	H	Art.Alp.	L-140		●		E4.3, E4.392			
470. <i>Thesium linophyllum</i> subsp. <i>montanum</i> (Schrad.) Čelak.	H	Europ.	N/A		●		E1.2			
471. <i>Thesium parnassi</i> A. DC.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A		●		E4.4125			
PLUMBAGINACEAE										
472. <i>Armeria canescens</i> (Host) Boiss.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-562	●		NT	E4.41, E4.412, E4.4125			
POLYGONACEAE										
473. <i>Aconogonon alpinum</i> (All.) Schur	H	Paleotemp.	N/A		●		E1.74			
474. <i>Bistorta officinalis</i> Delarbre	G	Circumbor.	L-563		●		D2.2			
475. <i>Bistorta vivipara</i> (L.) Delarbre	G	Art.Alp.	L-336	●			F2.2, E4.34			
476. <i>Polygonum aviculare</i> L.	T	Cosmopol.	N/A	●			E5.4			
477. <i>Rumex acetosa</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-338		●		E1.2, E1.22			
478. <i>Rumex acetosella</i> L.	H	Subcosmop.	L-339	●			E1.2, E1.7, E4.34			
479. <i>Rumex alpinus</i> L.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-337	●	●		E5.58, F2.3			
480. <i>Rumex crispus</i> L.	H	Subcosmop.	L-340	●			E5.4, E5.2, E3.3			
AMARANTHACEAE										
481. <i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> L.	T	N. Amer.	L-652	●			I1.3, E5.4			
CARYOPHYLLACEAE										
482. <i>Arenaria rotundifolia</i> M. Bieb.	C	Art.Alp.	N/A	●			H3.15, H3.152			
483. <i>Arenaria serpyllifolia</i> L.	T	Subcosmop.	L-651	●	●		E1.12, E4.4			
484. <i>Cerastium alpinum</i> L.	H	Art.Alp.	L-184	●			E4.4, E4.42, E4.412, H3.152			
485. <i>Cerastium brachypetalum</i> Pers.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E1.2, E4.31			
486. <i>Cerastium cerastoides</i> (L.) Britton.	H	Art.Alp.	L-186	●			D2.2, E4.1, E4.3, E4.34, E4.5			
487. <i>Cerastium decalvans</i> Schloss. & Vuk.	C	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-187		●		H2.6, H3.2, H2.4		End(B)	
488. <i>Cerastium fontanum</i> subsp. <i>vulgare</i> (Hartm.) Greut. & Burd.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A		●		E1.2			
489. <i>Cerastium glomeratum</i> Thuill.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E1.92			
490. <i>Dianthus armeria</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-189	●			E1.2, E1.22, G1.7			
491. <i>Dianthus carthusianorum</i> L.	H	Centro-Eur.	L-696	●			E1.2, E1.22, E4.3			
492. <i>Dianthus cruentus</i> Griseb.	H	Balkan	L-241		●		E1.2, E1.7, E1.73		End(B)	
493. <i>Dianthus deltoides</i> subsp. <i>degenii</i> (Bald.) Strid.	H	Balkan	L-242				E1.7, E1.73, F2.231		End(B)	▼
494. <i>Dianthus gracilis</i> subsp. <i>armerioides</i> (Griseb.) Tutin	H	Balkan	L-342				E1.7		End(B)	▼
495. <i>Dianthus integer</i> subsp. <i>minutiflorus</i> (Halácsy) Bornm.	H	Balkan	L-243				E4.4, E4.41, E4.412, H2.4		End(B)	
496. <i>Dianthus scardicus</i> Wettst.	H	Balkan	L-245	●	●	NT	E4.3, E4.31, E4.312, E1.112		End(B)	

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
497. <i>Dianthus superbus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-566		●	LC	E3.4, E3.5, E4.4126			
498. <i>Dianthus sylvestris</i> subsp. <i>bertisceus</i> Rech. f.	H	Balkan	L-246				E4.5, E4.4122, H2.4, E1.112		End(B)	
499. <i>Dianthus sylvestris</i> Wulfen subsp. <i>sylvestris</i>	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-247	●	●		E4.5, E4.41			
500. <i>Drypis spinosa</i> L.	H	Balkan	L-248	●		EN	H2.3			
501. <i>Herniaria glabra</i> L.	T	Paleotemp.	N/A	●			E1.92, G1.7			
502. <i>Minuartia graminifolia</i> subsp. <i>clandestina</i> (Port.) Mattf.	C	Medit.-Mont.	L-250				E1.92, H3.15		End(B)	
503. <i>Minuartia recurva</i> (All.) Schinz & Thell.	C	Euro-Cauc.	L-216	●			E4.3, E4.39, E4.3925, E4.34			
504. <i>Minuartia verna</i> (L.) Hiern.	C	Euro-Asiat.	L-217	●	●		E1.2, E1.22, E4.4, E4.41, H2.4			
505. <i>Moenchia mantica</i> (L.) Bartl.	T	Medit.-Mont.	L-218	●			E1.2, E1.22			
506. <i>Paronychia kapela</i> (Hacq.) A.Kern	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-219				E1.2, E4.4, E4.41			
507. <i>Paronychia macedonica</i> Chaudhri	H	Balkan	L-721				E4.41, E4.4126			
508. <i>Petrorhagia prolifera</i> (L.) P. W. Ball & Heywood	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			G1.7			
509. <i>Petrorhagia saxifraga</i> (L.) Link	H	Euri-Medit.	L-650	●			E1.2, H2.6, E1.92			
510. <i>Sagina subulata</i> (Sw.) C. Presl	H	Submedit.	L-220				D4.1			
511. <i>Saponaria officinalis</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-720				E5.4			
512. <i>Scleranthus perennis</i> subsp. <i>marginatus</i> (Guss.) Nyman	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-264	●	●		E1.22, E4.3, E4.31, E4.34			
513. <i>Silene asterias</i> Griseb.	G	Balkan	L-567	●		NT	D2.2, D2.26, D2.282		End(B)	
514. <i>Silene bupleuroides</i> subsp. <i>staticifolia</i> (Sm.) Chowdhuri	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-265				E1.2			
515. <i>Silene ciliata</i> Pourr.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-266		●		E1.112, E1.92			
516. <i>Silene coronaria</i> (L.) Clairv.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-568	●			F3.242, G1.7			
517. <i>Silene dioica</i> (L.) Clairv.	H	Paleotemp.	L-267				E5.5721			
518. <i>Silene flos-cuculi</i> (L.) Clairv.	H	Euro-Siber.	N/A	●			G1.7, E3.3			
519. <i>Silene italica</i> (L.) Pers.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-569	●			G1.7			
520. <i>Silene parnassica</i> Boiss. & Spruner subsp. <i>parnassica</i>	H	Balkan	L-268				E4.5		End(B)	
521. <i>Silene pusilla</i> Waldst. & Kit.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-269	●			D4.1, E4.41, D2.3, D2.38			
522. <i>Silene saxifraga</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-270	●	●		E4.4, E4.41, E4.412, H2.4			
523. <i>Silene sendtneri</i> Boiss.	H	Balkan	L-271	●	●		E1.22, E1.7, E4.31, E4.39, E4.34		End(B)	
524. <i>Silene viridiflora</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-570	●			F3.2421, G1.7, G1.A1			
525. <i>Silene viscaria</i> (L.) Jess.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-272	●	●		E1.73			
526. <i>Silene vulgaris</i> (Moench) Garcke subsp. <i>vulgaris</i>	H	Subcosmop.	L-273	●			E1.22, E1.73			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
527. <i>Silene vulgaris</i> subsp. <i>prostrata</i> (Gaudin) Schinz & Thell	H	Orof.SW.Eur.	L-274		●		E4.31			
528. <i>Silene waldsteinii</i> Griseb.	H	Balkan	L-275		●		H2.6, H3.15		End(B)	
529. <i>Spergularia rubra</i> (L.) J. Presl & C. Presl	T	Paleotemp.	L-276				E5.4, E5.43			
530. <i>Stellaria alsine</i> Grimm	H	Euro-Siber.	L-277				D2.2, D2.26, D2.38, D2.26			
531. <i>Stellaria graminea</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-278		●		E1.2, E1.7, E4.39, D2.38			
532. <i>Stellaria holostea</i> L.	C	Euro-Cauc.	L-571	●	●		F3.2421, G1.6933, E4.392, G1.A1			
533. <i>Stellaria media</i> (L.) Cirillo	T	Cosmopol.	L-712				E5.58, G1.7			
534. <i>Stellaria nemorum</i> L. subsp. <i>nemorum</i>	H	Europ.	L-280				D2.28			
CHENOPODIACEAE										
535. <i>Atriplex patula</i> L.	T	Euro-Siber.	L-649	●			E5.4			
536. <i>Blitum bonus-henricus</i> (L.) Rchb.	H	Europ.	L-697	●			E5.4			
CORNACEAE										
537. <i>Cornus mas</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-572	●			F3.2421, G1.A1			
538. <i>Cornus sanguinea</i> L.	P	Euro-Siber.	L-573	●			F3.2421, G1.1, G1.A1			
PRIMULACEAE										
539. <i>Anagallis arvensis</i> L.	T	Cosmopol.	L-698	●			E5.43			
540. <i>Anagallis foemina</i> Mill.	T	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E5.43			
541. <i>Cyclamen hederifolium</i> Aiton	G	Euri-Medit.	L-574	●			G1.7			
542. <i>Lysimachia nummularia</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-648	●			G1.7, G1.A1			
543. <i>Lysimachia punctata</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-347				G1.69322, G1.6933, E5.2			
544. <i>Lysimachia vulgaris</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-575	●			D2.2, D2.22		LC	
545. <i>Primula acaulis</i> (L.) L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-348	●			G1.6924, G1.7, E5.2, G1.A1			
546. <i>Primula elatior</i> subsp. <i>intricata</i> (Gren. & Godr.) Widmer	H	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A		●		E4.392			
547. <i>Primula minima</i> L.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-350	●	●		F2.2, E4.3, E4.39			
548. <i>Primula veris</i> subsp. <i>columnae</i> (Ten.) Lüdi	H	Europ.	L-352	●			F3.242			
549. <i>Soldanella alpina</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-353		●		E4.3, E4.31, E4.34			
ERICACEAE										
550. <i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i> (L.) Spreng	C	Art.Alp.	L-375	●	●		E4.4, E4.41, E4.4122, E4.34		LC	
551. <i>Bruckenthalia spiculifolia</i> Griseb.	C	Balkan	L-376	●	●		E1.7, E1.73, E3.5, E4.3, E4.34			
552. <i>Empetrum hermaphroditum</i> Hagerup	C	Circumbor.	L-377		●		E4.3, E4.39			
553. <i>Rhododendron ferrugineum</i> L.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-378		●	LC	F2.2, F2.22			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
554. <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L.	C	Circumbor.	L-379	●	●		E1.71, F2.22, E4.34, G3.1, H2.3			
555. <i>Vaccinium uliginosum</i> L.	C	Circumbor.	L-380	●	●		F2.2, E4.3, H2.3			
RUBIACEAE										
556. <i>Asperula aristata</i> L. f.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-647		●	VU	F2.231, G1.7C1			
557. <i>Asperula arvensis</i> L.	T	Euri-Medit.	L-576	●			E5.4			
558. <i>Asperula cynanchica</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-364	●			E4.4126, E4.41731, F2.231, H2.4			
559. <i>Asperula doerfleri</i> Wettst.	C	Balkan	L-470	●		LC	E4.4, H3.2A13			End(B)
560. <i>Asperula longiflora</i> Waldst. & Kit.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-577		●		E1.2, E4.4			
561. <i>Asperula taurina</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			G1.6933, G1.A1			
562. <i>Cruciata laevipes</i> Opiz	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2			
563. <i>Galium album</i> Mill. subsp. <i>album</i>	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-578		●		E4.4, E4.41			
564. <i>Galium anisophyllum</i> Vill.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-365	●	●		E4.3, E4.39, H2.4			
565. <i>Galium aparine</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E5.43, G1.6933, E5.2, G1.A1			
566. <i>Galium corradifolium</i> Vill.	H	Steno-Medit.	L-366	●			G1.7, H2.6, H2.6B			
567. <i>Galium flavescens</i> Borbás ex Simonk	H	Balkan	L-367				E4.413, E4.413A			
568. <i>Galium debile</i> Desv.	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E5.4, E5.43			
569. <i>Galium mollugo</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-368	●			E1.2, F2.32, E5.2			
570. <i>Galium odoratum</i> (L.) Scop.	G	Euro-Cauc.	L-369	●			G1.6933, G3.17, E5.3, E5.4, E5.2			
571. <i>Galium palustre</i> L.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-370				D2.2, D2.38, E3.3			
572. <i>Galium pumilum</i> Murray	H	Subatlant.	L-371				E1.2, G1.7, E5.3			
573. <i>Sherardia arvensis</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.92, D2.26			
GENTIANACEAE										
574. <i>Gentiana albanica</i> (Jáv.) A. W. Hill	H	Balkan	N/A		●		E1.7, E1.73			End(B)
575. <i>Gentiana punctata</i> L.	H	Orof.C.Eur.	L-196		●	LC	E1.7, E1.71			
576. <i>Gentiana utriculosa</i> L.	T	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-177				E1.2, E1.92, E4.392			
577. <i>Gentiana verna</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-178		●		E4.4, E4.41, E3.5			
578. <i>Gentianella bulgarica</i> (Velen) Holub.	T	Balkan	L-179			VU	E1.7, E1.73, E1.92, E4.3, E4.34			
APOCYNACEAE										
579. <i>Vinca herbacea</i> Waldst. & Kit.	C	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E1.2			
580. <i>Vinca major</i> L.	C	Euri-Medit.	L-579	●			E5.43			
581. <i>Vincetoxicum fuscatum</i> (Hornem.) Rchb. f.	G	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2			
582. <i>Vincetoxicum hirundinaria</i> Medik.	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			G4.6			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
OLEACEAE										
583. <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> L.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-261	●			G1.7, G1.A1, G1.1, G1.6933			
584. <i>Ligustrum vulgare</i> L.	P	Euro-Cauc.	L-262	●			F3.2421, G1.A1			
PLANTAGINACEAE										
585. <i>Digitalis ferruginea</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-580	●			F2.24, F2.231			
586. <i>Digitalis grandiflora</i> Mill.	H	Orof.SE-Eur.	L-381	●			E5.43, E5.5, F2.231			
587. <i>Digitalis laevigata</i> Waldst. & Kit.	H	Balkan	L-581	●			F3.2421, G1.7			
588. <i>Digitalis lanata</i> Ehrh.	H	Balkan	N/A	●			E5.43, G1.7			
589. <i>Globularia cordifolia</i> L.	C	Medit.-Mont.	L-382	●			E4.4, E4.41, F3.2421, E1.22			
590. <i>Globularia meridionalis</i> (Podp.) O. Schwarz	C	Medit.-Mont.	N/A		●		E4.1, E4.5			
591. <i>Gratiola officinalis</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-582	●			D2.22	LC		
592. <i>Linaria alpina</i> (L.) Mill.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-383	●		CR	H2.6, H2.6B, H2.3			
593. <i>Linaria angustissima</i> (Loisel.) Borbás	H	Orof.SE-Eur.	L-384	●			F3.2421, G1.7			
594. <i>Linaria pelisseriana</i> (L.) Mill.	T	Medit.-Mont.	N/A	●			E1.7			
595. <i>Linaria peloponnesiaca</i> Boiss. & Heldr.	H	Balkan	L-385	●			E4.392, E4.412		End(B)	
596. <i>Linaria vulgaris</i> Mill.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-583	●			E1.7, F3.242, E4.39			
597. <i>Plantago atrata</i> Hoppe	H	Europ.	L-471	●	●		E4.1, E4.116, E4.12, E4.14			
598. <i>Plantago gentianoides</i> Sibth. & Sm.	H	Balkan	L-472			LC	E4.1, E4.14, E4.5			
599. <i>Plantago holosteum</i> Scop.	H	Europ.	L-386	●			E1.92, E4.4, E4.41			
600. <i>Plantago lanceolata</i> L.	H	Cosmopol.	L-387	●			E1.2, E5.2, E3.3			
601. <i>Plantago major</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-388	●			E3.4, E4.39, E5.2			
602. <i>Plantago media</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-584	●			E1.2, E1.22			
603. <i>Plantago reniformis</i> Beck	H	Balkan	L-473	●		NT	E5.51, E5.58, E4.4121		End(B)	
604. <i>Veronica alpina</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E4.1, E4.39, E4.5			
605. <i>Veronica aphylla</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-474	●			E4.412, E4.4125, E4.3925			
606. <i>Veronica arvensis</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-585	●			E5.43			
607. <i>Veronica austriaca</i> L.	H	Centro-Eur.	L-389				E1.2, F3.2421, E1.7			
608. <i>Veronica austriaca</i> subsp. <i>jacquinii</i> (Baumg.) Eb. Fisch.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-390	●			E1.22			
609. <i>Veronica austriaca</i> subsp. <i>teucrium</i> (L.) D. A. Webb	H	Centro-Eur.	L-391				E1.7, E1.73			▼
610. <i>Veronica beccabunga</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-392				E3.4, E3.5, D2.38, D2.26	LC		
611. <i>Veronica chamaedrys</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-393	●	●		E1.22, E5.2, E4.34, G3.1, G1.A1			
612. <i>Veronica fruticans</i> Jacq.	C	Art.Alp.	L-394				E4.39			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
613. <i>Veronica officinalis</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A		●		F2.23, F2.231, G1.6933, G3.1			
614. <i>Veronica orsiniana</i> Ten.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-395				E4.392, E4.3925			
615. <i>Veronica persica</i> Poir.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-396	●			G1.7			
616. <i>Veronica serpyllifolia</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-397				E5.51, E5.5721, G1.A1			▼
617. <i>Veronica thessalica</i> Benth.	H	Balkan	L-586	●		CR	H2.6, H3.2A13		End(B)	
SCROPHULARIACEAE										
618. <i>Scrophularia canina</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E1.22, E4.312			
619. <i>Scrophularia heterophylla</i> subsp. <i>laciniata</i> (Wald. & Kit.) Mai. & Pet.	H	Balkan	L-343				E1.22, H3.2A13, H2.4, H2.3			
620. <i>Scrophularia nodosa</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-344	●			G1.6933, G4.6, E5.2, G1.A1			
621. <i>Verbascum longifolium</i> subsp. <i>pannosum</i> (Vis. & Pančić) Murb.	H	Balkan	N/A		●		E4.4125			
622. <i>Verbascum nigrum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-587	●			E1.2, E1.73, E1.74			
623. <i>Verbascum phoeniceum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2, G1.7, E4.5			
ACANTHACEAE										
624. <i>Acanthus hungaricus</i> (Borbás) Baen.	H	Balkan	L-699	●			G1.7			
GESNERIACEAE										
625. <i>Ramonda nathaliae</i> Pančić & Petrovič	H	Balkan	L-588			EN	H3.2, G1.7C1, H3.2A13		End(B)	
LAMIACEAE										
626. <i>Ajuga chamaepitys</i> (L.) Schreb.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-589	●			E1.22			
627. <i>Ajuga genevensis</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-590	●			E1.22, E1.7, E1.73, G1.A1			
628. <i>Ajuga laxmannii</i> (Murray) Benth.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-591	●			G1.7			
629. <i>Ajuga pyramidalis</i> L.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-281	●			E1.7, E1.92			
630. <i>Ajuga reptans</i> L.	G	Euro-Asiat.	L-592	●			G1.6933, G1.A1			
631. <i>Clinopodium acinos</i> (L.) Kunzte	T	Euri-Medit.	L-282	●			E5.43			
632. <i>Clinopodium alpinum</i> (L.) Kuntze subsp. <i>alpinum</i>	C	Orof.S.Eur.	L-283	●	●		E4.41, E4.4126, E4.41731			
633. <i>Clinopodium alpinum</i> subsp. <i>hungaricum</i> (Simonk.) Govaerts	H	Balkan	N/A	●			E4.41731			
634. <i>Clinopodium grandiflorum</i> (L.) Kuntze	T	Orof.S.Eur.	L-284		●		F2.231, F2.2, E5.2			
635. <i>Clinopodium menthifolium</i> (Host) Stace subsp. <i>menthifolium</i>	H	Euro-Cauc.	N/A	●			E5.43			
636. <i>Clinopodium vulgare</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-285				E1.22, F3.2421, G1.A1			
637. <i>Glechoma hirsuta</i> Waldst. & Kit.	H	Europ.	N/A	●			G1.6933, G1.A1			
638. <i>Lamium amplexicaule</i> L.	T	Paleotemp.	L-593	●			E5.4			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
639. <i>Lamium galeobdolon</i> (L.) Crantz	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-286	●			G1.6933, G4.6, E5.2, G1.A1			
640. <i>Lamium purpureum</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-594	●			G1.7, E4.413			
641. <i>Melittis melissophyllum</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-595	●			F3.2421, G1.69322, G1.6933			
642. <i>Mentha longifolia</i> (L.) L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-287	●			D2.2, D2.22, E5.2, D2.38, D2.26			
643. <i>Mentha pulegium</i> L.	H	Medit.	L-713				E3.4, E5.5	LC		
644. <i>Origanum vulgare</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-288				E1.2, E1.22, E4.4			
645. <i>Prunella laciniata</i> (L.) L.	H	Medit.	N/A	●			E1.22, E1.7, E1.73, E1.74			
646. <i>Prunella vulgaris</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-289	●			E1.22, E1.7, E3.4, E5.2, D2.38			
647. <i>Salvia nemorosa</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-596	●			E1.2, E1.22, F3.2421			
648. <i>Salvia verticillata</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-290	●			E1.22, E1.7, E3.4, E5.43, E5.2			
649. <i>Satureja montana</i> L. subsp. <i>montana</i>	C	Medit.	L-291				E1.22, F3.2421			
650. <i>Scutellaria alpina</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-292			EN	E4.4, H3.2, H3.2A13, H3.15			
651. <i>Sideritis scardica</i> Griseb.	H	Balkan	L-293			CR	E1.2, E4.4126, E4.41		End(B)	
652. <i>Stachys alopecuroides</i> (L.) Benth.	H	Europ.	L-294				F2.231, F2.32, E4.4125			
653. <i>Stachys alpina</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-295	●			E4.413A, E4.39, E4.3925			
654. <i>Stachys germanica</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-296	●	●		E1.2, E1.22, G1.7			
655. <i>Stachys officinalis</i> (L.) Trevis.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-597	●			E1.22, E1.7, E1.73			
656. <i>Stachys plumosa</i> Griseb.	H	Balkan	N/A	●			E4.39, E4.392		End(B)	
657. <i>Stachys recta</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-598	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.55			
658. <i>Stachys scardica</i> (Griseb.) Hayek	H	Balkan	L-297	●			E1.2, G1.7, G4.6		End(B)	
659. <i>Stachys sylvatica</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-599	●			G4.6, G1.7, E5.4, G1.6933, G1.A1			
660. <i>Stachys tymphaea</i> Hausskn.	H	Medit.-Mont.	N/A	●			E4.41			
661. <i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i> L.	C	Euri-Medit.	L-298	●			E1.22, E4.41731, E4.42, E5.2			
662. <i>Teucrium montanum</i> L.	C	Orof.S.Eur.	L-299	●	●		E1.55, F3.2421			
663. <i>Teucrium polium</i> L.	C	Steno-Medit.	N/A	●			F3.2421			
664. <i>Thymus longicaulis</i> C. Presl subsp. <i>longicaulis</i>	C	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E1.22			
665. <i>Thymus praecox</i> subsp. <i>zygiformis</i> (Heinr.Braun ex Wett.) Jalas	C	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-327	●	●		E4.3, E4.39, E4.392, E4.34, H2.4		End(B)	

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
666. <i>Thymus pulegioides</i> L.	C	Euro-Asiat.	L-328				E1.2, E1.22, E1.74, F2.231			
OROBANCHACEAE										
667. <i>Euphrasia minima</i> DC.	T	Orof.C.Eur.	L-600	●	●		E4.3, E4.39, E4.3925 E1.71, E1.73, E3.5, E4.34, E1.112			
668. <i>Euphrasia rostkoviana</i> Hayene	T	Euro-Siber.	L-341				E1.2, E1.22, E4.4, E4.41731			
669. <i>Euphrasia salisburgensis</i> Funck	T	Euro-Cauc.	L-601	●	●		E1.22, E1.73, E1.74, F2.263			
670. <i>Euphrasia stricta</i> J. F. Lehm.	T	Europ.	L-700	●			G1.7, F3.2421			
671. <i>Melampyrum pratense</i> L.	T	Euro-Siber.	L-602	●			F2.22, F2.231, F2.3			End(B)
672. <i>Melampyrum scardicum</i> Wettst.	T	Balkan	L-603	●		LC	E1.22, E1.73			
673. <i>Orobanche caryophyllacea</i> Sm.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-359				E1.92			
674. <i>Parentucellia latifolia</i> (L.) Caruel	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E4.412, E4.4122			End(B)
675. <i>Pedicularis brachyodonta</i> subsp. <i>grisebachii</i> (Wettst.) Hayek	H	Balkan	L-604		●	LC	E1.22			
676. <i>Pedicularis friderici-augusti</i> Tomm.	H	Medit.-Mont.	N/A		●		E4.39, E4.392			
677. <i>Pedicularis oederi</i> Vahl	H	Circumbor.	N/A	●			E4.3, E4.39, E4.392			
678. <i>Pedicularis verticillata</i> L.	H	Art.Alp.	L-605	●	●		E1.2, E1.7, E1.73, E1.92			
679. <i>Rhinanthus minor</i> L.	T	Circumbor.	L-606	●			E1.2, E1.7, E1.73			
680. <i>Rhinanthus rumelicus</i> Velen.	T	Medit.-Mont.	N/A	●						
VERBENACEAE										
681. <i>Verbena officinalis</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-361				E3.4, E5.3, E5.4, E5.2			
LENTIBULARIACEA										
682. <i>Pinguicula balcanica</i> Casper.	H	Balkan	L-177	●		NT	D2.22, D2.26, D2.282. D2.38, D4.2			End(B)
CONVOLVULACEAE										
683. <i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.	G	Paleotemp.	L-607	●			E1.2, E1.7, E1.73, E1.92			
684. <i>Convolvulus boissieri</i> subsp. <i>compactus</i> (Boiss.) Stace	C	Balkan	N/A	●			E1.2			End(B)
685. <i>Convolvulus cantabrica</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-608	●			E1.2, E1.55			
SOLANACEAE										
686. <i>Atropa bella-donna</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-354	●			G1.6924, E5.4, E5.2 E5.5, E5.51			
687. <i>Datura stramonium</i> L.	T	Cosmopol.	L-609	●						
BORAGINACEAE										
688. <i>Buglossoides arvensis</i> (L.) I. M. Johnst.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E5.4 E1.7, E1.76, E1.74, E1.92			
689. <i>Cerinthe minor</i> L.	T	Euro-Siber.	L-610	●						
690. <i>Myosotis alpestris</i> Hoffm.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-329	●	●		E4.12, E4.3, E4.39, E4.5			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
691. <i>Myosotis suaveolens</i> Willd.	H	Balkan	L-330				F2.231, F2.263, H2.4		End(B)	
692. <i>Myosotis sylvatica</i> Hoffm.	H	Paleotemp.	L-331	●			G1.6933, E5.43, G3.1, G1.A1			
693. <i>Pulmonaria officinalis</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-333	●			G4.6, G1.6933, E5.43, E5.2, G1.A1			
694. <i>Pulmonaria rubra</i> Schott.	H	Balkan	L-334				E5.43, G1.6933			
695. <i>Symphytum tuberosum</i> L.	G	Euri-Medit.	L-611	●	●		E4.3, G4.6, E5.43, G3.1			
ARALIACEAE										
696. <i>Hedera helix</i> L.	P	Euri-Medit.	L-335	●			F3.2421, G4.6, E5.2, G1.A1			
APIACEAE										
697. <i>Aegopodium podagraria</i> L.	G	Euro-Siber.	L-401	●			E3.4, E3.5, F2.231, E5.2, G1.A1			
698. <i>Angelica sylvestris</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-402				E4.412, G3.12			
699. <i>Anthriscus caucalis</i> M. Bieb.	T	Euri-Medit.	L-403				E5.43			
700. <i>Astrantia major</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-612	●			E4.4126, E4.41731, E4.4122			
701. <i>Bifora radians</i> M. Bieb.	T	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E3.4, E5.43			
702. <i>Bupleurum falcatum</i> subsp. <i>cernuum</i> (Ten.) Arc.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-404	●			E4.41			
703. <i>Bupleurum karglii</i> Vis.	T	Balkan	L-405	●			E4.312, E4.392, E4.412		End(B)	
704. <i>Bupleurum ranunculoides</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-613		●		E4.4, E4.41, E4.4121			
705. <i>Bupleurum veronense</i> Turra	T	Orof.SE.Eur.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.55			
706. <i>Chaerophyllum aromaticum</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-406				E5.4, G1.7, E1.2			
707. <i>Chaerophyllum aureum</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-407				E1.2, E1.22			
708. <i>Chaerophyllum hirsutum</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-408				E5.4, E5.43, E5.5, E5.2			
709. <i>Daucus carota</i> L.	T	Paleotemp.	L-614	●			E5.4			
710. <i>Eryngium campestre</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-615	●			F3.2421			
711. <i>Eryngium palmatum</i> Pančić & Vis.	H	Balkan	N/A	●			G1.7		End(B)	
712. <i>Laser trilobum</i> (L.) Borkh.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-616	●			G1.7			
713. <i>Ligusticum mutellina</i> (L.) Crantz	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-409	●	●		E1.7, E4.3, E4.39, E4.34			
714. <i>Meum athamanticum</i> Jacq.	H	Europ.	L-410				E4.39, E4.392			
715. <i>Oenanthe fistulosa</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			D5.131	LC		
716. <i>Oenanthe peucedanifolia</i> Pollich.	H	Medit.	L-411	●			E4.116, E4.5			
717. <i>Oenanthe silaifolia</i> M. Bieb.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E5.4, E5.5721			
718. <i>Orlaya grandiflora</i> (L.) Hoffm.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-617	●			E1.22, E1.55, E5.4			
719. <i>Physospermum cornubiense</i> (L.) DC.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-412				G1.7			
720. <i>Pimpinella alpina</i> Koord.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-413	●			E4.3, E4.312			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
721. <i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i> L.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-414	●	●		E1.2, E4.3, E4.312, E4.34			
722. <i>Sanicula europaea</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-618	●			G1.7, G1.6933, G4.6, G3.1, G1.A1			
723. <i>Scandix pecten-veneris</i> L.	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E5.43			
724. <i>Seseli montanum</i> L.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-619	●			F3.2421, H3.1			
725. <i>Smyrniium perfoliatum</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			F3.2421, G1.6933			
726. <i>Trinia dalechampii</i> (Ten.) Janch.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-416	●			E4.41, E4.4126, E4.34			
727. <i>Trinia glauca</i> (L.) Dumort	H	Europ.	L-417	●	●		F2.2, F2.23			
VIBURNACEAE										
728. <i>Sambucus ebulus</i> L.	G	Euri-Medit.	L-238	●			E4.1, F3.2421, G1.7, G4.6, E5.2			
729. <i>Sambucus nigra</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-239	●			E5.43, E5.5, E5.2, G1.A1			
730. <i>Sambucus racemosa</i> L.	P	Euro-Asiat.	L-240	●			G4.6, E5.43, E5.2			
CAPRIFOLIACEAE										
731. <i>Lonicera alpigena</i> L.	P	Orof.S.Eur.	L-263	●			G1.6933, G4.6, E5.2			
732. <i>Lonicera caprifolium</i> L.	P	Europ.	L-620	●			G4.6, G1.A1			
733. <i>Viburnum lantana</i> L.	C	Europ.	L-621	●			F3.2421, G1.A1			
DIPSACACEAE										
734. <i>Cephalaria leucantha</i> (L.) Roem. & Schult.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-622	●			E1.2			
735. <i>Dipsacus fullonum</i> L.	H	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E5.43			
736. <i>Knautia arvensis</i> (L.) DC.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-193	●	●		E1.2, E1.22			
737. <i>Knautia drymeia</i> Heuff.	H	Europ.	N/A	●			G1.6933, G4.6, E4.312			
738. <i>Knautia midzorensis</i> Formánek	H	Balkan	L-646	●	●	EN	E4.4, E4.41, E4.4122		End(B)	
739. <i>Scabiosa columbaria</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-194	●			F2.2, E4.392, E4.3925, E4.41			
740. <i>Scabiosa taygetea</i> subsp. <i>portae</i> (Huter) Kokkini	H	Balkan	L-645	●	●		E4.312, F2.231		End(B)	
VALERIANACEAE										
741. <i>Valeriana montana</i> Griseb.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-236				E5.5, E5.51, H3.15			
742. <i>Valeriana officinalis</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-237				E1.74, E1.92, E3.4			
CAMPANULACEAE										
743. <i>Asyneuma limonifolium</i> (L.) Janch.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-429	●			E1.5, E1.7			
744. <i>Campanula abietina</i> Griseb.	H	Balkan	L-716				E1.7		DD	
745. <i>Campanula alpina</i> Jacq.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-623	●	●	LC	E4.392, E4.3925, F2.11			
746. <i>Campanula foliosa</i> Ten.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-430		●	LC	F2.263, F2.231, E5.43			
747. <i>Campanula glomerata</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-431	●			E4.4, E1.2, E1.22, E1.7			
748. <i>Campanula patula</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-433				E1.2, E1.7, E1.73, E1.74			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
749. <i>Campanula persicifolia</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-434	●			F3.2421, G1.6933, E5.2, G1.A1			
750. <i>Campanula rotundifolia</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-435	●	●	EN	E4.3, E4.312, E4.39, E4.34, H2.4			
751. <i>Campanula scheuchzeri</i> Vill.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-644	●	●		E1.7, E1.73, E4.3, E4.39			
752. <i>Campanula spatulata</i> Sm. subsp. <i>spatulata</i>	G	Balkan	L-624		●		E4.39			End(B)
753. <i>Campanula trachelium</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-437	●			G1.6933, E5.43, E5.2, G1.A1			
754. <i>Edraianthus graminifolius</i> (L.) A.DC.	C	Balkan	L-438	●	●		E4.4, E4.412, E1.112			
755. <i>Jasione orbiculata</i> Griseb.	H	Balkan	L-439	●	●		F2.2, E1.7, E4.3, E4.39, E4.34			
756. <i>Phyteuma confusum</i> A. Kern.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-625	●	●		E4.3, E4.39, E4.3925			
757. <i>Phyteuma orbiculare</i> L.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A	●			E4.3, E4.392			
758. <i>Phyteuma pseudorbiculare</i> Pant.	H	Balkan	L-440		●	LC	E4.3, E4.39			End(B)
ASTERACEAE										
759. <i>Achillea abrotanoides</i> (Vis.) Vis	C	Balkan	L-355		●		F2.32, H3.2A13			End(B)
760. <i>Achillea ageratifolia</i> (Sm.) Benth. & Hook. f. subsp. <i>ageratifolia</i>	H	Balkan	L-565				E4.41, H2.4			End(B)
761. <i>Achillea chrysocoma</i> Friv.	H	Balkan	L-358	●	●	EN	E4.41, E4.4126, F2.231			End(B)
762. <i>Achillea clusiana</i> Tausch	H	Balkan	L-363				F2.22, F2.263			
763. <i>Achillea coerctata</i> Poir.	H	Europ.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.22			
764. <i>Achillea distans</i> subsp. <i>tanacetifolia</i> (Fiori) Janch.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A		●		E5.4			
765. <i>Achillea millefolium</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-362	●	●		E5.43, E4.413, E4.413A			
766. <i>Achillea nobilis</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.7			
767. <i>Achillea setacea</i> Waldst. et Kit.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-441				E1.2, E1.7, E1.92			
768. <i>Adenostyles alliariae</i> (Gouan) A. Kern.	H	Europ.	L-626	●			G1.6933, F2.11, E5.43			
769. <i>Antennaria dioica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	C	Circumbor.	L-442	●	●		E1.71, E4.3, E4.39, E4.34, E1.112			
770. <i>Anthemis arvensis</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-627	●			E1.2			
771. <i>Anthemis cretica</i> subsp. <i>carpatica</i> (Willd.) Grierson	H	Europ.	L-717				E4.3, E4.39, E4.3922			
772. <i>Arctium lappa</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-443				E5.43, E5.5, E5.2			
773. <i>Artemisia umbelliformis</i> subsp. <i>eriantha</i> (Ten.) Vallès-Xirau & Oliva Brañas	C	Orof.S.Eur.	L-444			EN	E4.3925, H3.15, H3.152			
774. <i>Artemisia vulgaris</i> L.	H	Circumbor.	L-445				E5.43, E5.2			
775. <i>Aster alpinus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-446	●	●		E4.4, E4.41, E4.4121, H2.4			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
776. <i>Bellis perennis</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-447	●			E1.2, E1.22, E4.312, E4.39			
777. <i>Carduus acanthoides</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-421				E1.2, E4.34			
778. <i>Carduus candicans</i> Wald et Kit.	H	Balkan	L-422	●			E4.392, F2.231, E1.2			
779. <i>Carduus carduelis</i> (L.) Gren.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A		●		E4.3, E4.39, E4.392			
780. <i>Carlina acaulis</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-374				E1.2, E1.22, E1.74, E1.92, E4.34			
781. <i>Centaurea jacea</i> L.	H	Euro-Siber.	N/A	●			E1.2, E1.22, E1.92			
782. <i>Centaurea nervosa</i> Willd.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-628	●			E4.3, E4.31, E4.39			
783. <i>Cirsium appendiculatum</i> Griseb.	H	Balkan	L-398	●			E5.57, E5.5721		End(B)	
784. <i>Cirsium arvense</i> (L.) Scop.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-399	●			E5.43, E3.4, F2.231, E5.2, G1.1			
785. <i>Cirsium canum</i> (L.) All.	G	Orof.S.Eur.	N/A	●			E3.4			
786. <i>Cirsium eriophorum</i> (L.) Scop.	H	Europ.	L-400	●			E1.22, E1.7, E1.71			
787. <i>Crepis aurea</i> subsp. <i>glabrescens</i> (Caurel.) Ar.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-424				E4.412			
788. <i>Crepis viscidula</i> Froel.	H	Balkan	N/A		●		E4.3, E4.39			
789. <i>Crupina vulgaris</i> Cass.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-629	●			E1.7			
790. <i>Cyanus segetum</i> Hill	T	Euri-Medit.	N/A	●			E5.43, E5.5			
791. <i>Cyanus triumfettii</i> subsp. <i>axillaris</i> (Čelak.) Štěpánek	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-373	●	●		E4.41, E4.412			
792. <i>Doronicum austriacum</i> Jacq.	G	Orof.S.Eur.	L-418	●			E5.57, E5.5721, G1.6933			
793. <i>Doronicum columnae</i> Ten.	G	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-419	●	●		E4.3, E4.39, E4.392, F2.32			
794. <i>Erigeron alpinus</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-425	●			H3.152			
795. <i>Erigeron annuus</i> (L.) Desf.	T	N. Amer.	L-426				E5.43, E5.2			
796. <i>Erigeron glabratus</i> Bluff & Fingerh.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-630		●		E4.391, E4.392			
797. <i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i> L.	H	Paleotemp.	L-420				G1.6933, G4.6, E5.2			
798. <i>Filago germanica</i> (L.) Huds.	T	Paleotemp.	N/A	●			E1.92			
799. <i>Galatella linosyris</i> (L.) Rchb. f.	H	Paleotemp.	N/A	●			E1.92			
800. <i>Gnaphalium supinum</i> L.	H	Arctic-Alp.	L-631	●			E4.1, E4.116, E4.5			
801. <i>Hieracium bosniacum</i> Freyn	H	Balkan	L-722				E4.412, E4.4121		End(B)	
802. <i>Hieracium murorum</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-457		●		E5.43, G4.6, G1.6933, E5.2, G1.A1			
803. <i>Hieracium naegelianum</i> Pančić subsp. <i>naegelianum</i>	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-458				E4.392, E4.3925			
804. <i>Hieracium naegelianum</i> subsp. <i>ljubotenicum</i> O. Behr & al.	H	Balkan	L-719				E4.3411		End(B)	
805. <i>Hieracium piliferum</i> Hoppe	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	N/A	●			E4.41			
806. <i>Hieracium pilosum</i> Froel. subsp. <i>pilosum</i>	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-459				E4.412			

Annex. 1 - cont.

	FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
807.	<i>Hieracium pilosum</i> subsp. <i>villosiceps</i> Gottschl.	H	Orof. S-Europ.	L-723				E4.3411			▼
808.	<i>Hieracium sparsum</i> Friv.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A		●		E4.4121			
809.	<i>Hieracium villosum</i> Jacq.	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-460				E1.7, E1.74, E1.92, H3.2, H2.4			
810.	<i>Homogyne alpina</i> (L.) Cast.	H	Europ.	L-454	●	●		E4.39, E4.4125, H3.2A13			
811.	<i>Inula ensifolia</i> L.	H	Europ.	L-632	●			E1.2, E1.71, E1.74, H2.6			
812.	<i>Inula oculus-christi</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.92			
813.	<i>Inula salicina</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-633	●			E1.7, E1.74, E3.3			
814.	<i>Jacobaea abrotanifolia</i> subsp. <i>carpathica</i> (Herbich) B. Nord. & Greuter	C	Medit.-Mont.	L-643	●	●		E4.39, E4.391			
815.	<i>Lactuca muralis</i> (L.) Gaertn.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-451	●			G1.6933, G4.6, E5.4, E5.2, G1.A1	LC		
816.	<i>Lapsana communis</i> L.	T	Paleotemp.	L-452	●			G1.6933, E5.4, E5.2, G1.A1			
817.	<i>Leontodon biscutellifolius</i> DC.	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			E1.22, E4.41			
818.	<i>Leontodon crispus</i> Vill.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-427				E1.22, E4.5, G1.7, H2.4			
819.	<i>Leontodon hispidus</i> L.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-428	●			E1.2, E1.7, E1.73, E1.74			
820.	<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> (Vaill.) Lam.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-463	●			E1.2, E1.72, E1.73, E5.4			
821.	<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> L.	T	Cosmopol.	L-634	●			E5.43			
822.	<i>Petasites albus</i> (L.) Gaertn.	G	Europ.	L-464				G1.6933, G1.7, G4.6, E5.43			
823.	<i>Pilosella acutifolia</i> (Vill.) Arv.-Touv.	H	Europ.	L-455				F2.11, F2.12			
824.	<i>Pilosella alpicola</i> (Hoppe) F. W. Schultz & Sch. Bip.	H	Orof.S.Eur.	L-635	●			F2.231, F2.263, F2.22			
825.	<i>Pilosella cymosa</i> (L.) F. W. Schultz & Sch. Bip.	H	Europ.	L-465	●			E1.22, E1.71, E4.39			
826.	<i>Pilosella guthnikiana</i> (Hegetschw.) Soják	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A		●		E4.3411			
827.	<i>Pilosella hoppeana</i> (Schult.) F. W. Schultz & Sch. Bip.	H	Medit.-Mont.	L-456				E1.2, E1.92, E1.22, E1.7, E4.34			
828.	<i>Pilosella macrotricha</i> (Boiss.) F. W. Schultz & Sch. Bip.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-724				E4.4122			■ ■
829.	<i>Pilosella officinarum</i> Vaill.	H	Euro-Cauc.	L-466	●	●		E1.2, E1.22, E1.55, E4.34			
830.	<i>Podospermum laciniatum</i> (L.) DC.	T	Paleotemp.	N/A	●			E1.22, E4.41			
831.	<i>Podospermum roseum</i> (Waldst. & Kit.) Gemeinholzer & Greuter	H	Europ.	N/A	●			F3.2421			
832.	<i>Prenanthes purpurea</i> L.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-636	●			G1.7, G4.6			
833.	<i>Ptilostemon afer</i> (Jacq.) Greuter	H	Balkan	L-467		●		E4.41, E4.4122, H2.6			
834.	<i>Pulicaria dysenterica</i> (L.) Bernh.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-637	●			E3.4			

Annex. 1 - cont.

FAMILY / Taxon	Life	Flor. element	Herb.	R.84	R.90	XK	EUNIS code	EU	END	Note
835. <i>Scorzonera austriaca</i> Willd.	H	Euro-Siber.	L-638	●			G1.7, E5.43, E1.22			
836. <i>Scorzoneroides autumnalis</i> (L.) Moench	H	Euro-Siber.	N/A		●		E5.51, E5.5721			
837. <i>Senecio nemorensis</i> subsp. <i>bulgaricus</i> (Velen.) Greuter	H	Balkan	L-468	●	●		F2.22, G1.6933, G4.6, G3.1			
838. <i>Senecio squalidus</i> subsp. <i>rupestris</i> (Waldst. & Kit.) Greuter	H	Orof.SE.Eur.	L-469	●	●		F2.2, E5.43, G4.6			
839. <i>Senecio vulgaris</i> L.	T	Paleotemp.	L-639	●			E5.43			
840. <i>Serratula tinctoria</i> L.	T	Euro-Siber.	L-640	●			E5.43, E5.2			
841. <i>Tanacetum corymbosum</i> (L.) Sch. Bip.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-448	●			E1.7, E1.71, E1.73			
842. <i>Tanacetum larvatum</i> (Pant.) Hayek	C	Balkan	L-346				E3.4, E5.43		End(B)	▼
843. <i>Tanacetum macrophyllum</i> (Waldst. & Kit.) Sch. Bip.	H	Pontic.	L-449	●			G1.6933, G4.6, E5.2			
844. <i>Tanacetum parthenium</i> (L.) Sch. Bip.	H	Euri-Medit.	L-450	●			E5.4, G4.6, E5.2			
845. <i>Taraxacum alpinum</i> (Hoppe.) Heg. & Heer.- Handel-Mazz. [<i>Taraxacum</i> sect. <i>Erythrosperma</i> (H. Lindb.) Dahlst.]	H	Circumbor.	L-476				E4.392			
846. <i>Taraxacum laevigatum</i> (Willd.) DC. [<i>Taraxacum</i> sect. <i>Erythrosperma</i> (H. Lindb.) Dahlst.]	H	Paleotemp.	N/A		●		E1.22, E1.73			
847. <i>Taraxacum officinale</i> F. H. Wigg. (group) [<i>Taraxacum</i> sect. <i>Taraxacum</i> F. H. Wigg.]	H	Circumbor.	L-641	●	●		E1.2, E3.3			
848. <i>Taraxacum palustre</i> (Lyons) Symons	H	Euro-Asiat.	N/A	●			G4.6, G1.6933			
849. <i>Telekia speciosa</i> (Schreb.) Baumg.	H	Euro-Asiat.	L-453	●			E5.4, E5.43, E5.2			
850. <i>Tephrosia papposa</i> subsp. <i>wagneri</i> (Degen) B. Nord.	H	Balkan	L-461	●	●	VU	E4.3411, E4.39, E4.392		End(B)	
851. <i>Tragopogon pratensis</i> subsp. <i>orientalis</i> (L.) Čelak.	H	Euro-Siber.	N/A	●			E1.7			
852. <i>Willemetia stipitata</i> subsp. <i>albanica</i> (Kümmerle & Jáv.) Kirschnerová	H	Balkan	L-462				D2.282		End(B)	
853. <i>Xeranthemum annuum</i> L.	T	Euro-Asiat.	L-642	●			E1.2, E1.73, E4.43			

Table commentary:

FAMILY / Taxon – Plant family, followed by plant taxa (species and/or subspecies), **Life** – life form, **Flor. element** – Floristic element of the taxa, **Herb.** – Unique Herbarium Code of the Taxa (when indicated N/A, there is no Herbarium reference on the particular taxa, only literature data are used as reference), **R.1984** – Rexhepi, 1984 (see *References*), **R.1990** – Rajevski, 1990 (see *References*), **XK** – Status of plant taxa based on the Kosovarian Red List of plant taxa, **EUNIS code** - Habitat type according to EUNIS, **EU** - Red List status of European vascular plants, **END** – Status concerning Endemism, when so – ‘End(B) is added, meaning Endemic of Balkans, **Note** - Additional notes concerning the plant taxa, ▼ – new locality in Kosovo, ■ ■ – First record for Kosovo, **CONS. +** – Plant conservation and protection measures proposed.

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